
A gravitational interaction potential unifies gravity with other forces --the cornerstone of Theory of Everything

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* Because unorthodox natural of EIDIP framework, section 2 (empirical evidences) has been reordered to encourage readers to read it first.

EIDIP effects phenomenological tests (EEPT)

E-space interdomain interaction potential (EIDIP) effects can describe a wide range, from subatomic to intergalactic, of physical phenomena:

- EIDIP effect phenomenological tests (EEPT) are based on MATLAB simulations of distance and magnitude scaled *single parameter* T_c EIDIP effects functions against the publicly available empirical data or figures;
- The 10+ EEPTs in this section will show that, without conventional form factors, the EIDIP effects can describe a wide range of physical phenomena and anomalies: e.g., interquark [strong force](#) ([1].VII.A), [nucleon-neutron potential](#) ([1].VI.C), interatomic [covalent forces](#) ([1].VI.A), [nuclear binding energy](#) of known nuclei ([1].V.A), interatomic [Bohr radius](#) ([1].VII.B), [effective couplings \(electric, magnetic, residual-strong, and strong\)](#) and the related fine structure constant and Planck constant ([1].VIII.E), subatomic [neutron and proton charge distributions](#) ([1].VIII.A-D), astronomical [Pioneer 10/11 anomalies](#) ([1].VII.C) and [Milky Way rotation curve anomalies](#) ([1].VIII.F-G).

One cannot prove hypotheses or theories in physics:

- Because of unknown future discoveries, all known physical phenomena cannot be treated as a complete sampling space to prove a hypothesis or theory;
- It is fair to argue that one phenomenological fit can be coincidental; it is also fair to argue that the more EIDIP effects phenomenological fits, the less likely they are all coincidental;
- [Null hypothesis testing node \(NHTD\) method](#) can give a quantitative estimate to reject the null hypothesis that the EIDIP underlying the 10+ EEPTs doesn't exist (i.e., all these phenomenological fits are just coincidental);
- Null hypothesis testing node (NHTD) are partitioned into **primary (P-NHTD)** (for the phenomenological fitness and their [statistically uncanny scaling components](#)) and **secondary (S-NHTD)** (for the [statistically uncanny elements between EEPTs](#)); and those **yet** to be fully developed **Y-EEPT** and **Y-NHTD**;
- The [7+ Sigma significance](#) calculation are based on the **P-NHTD** only, each with a conservative 0.5 null probability (i.e., they are coincidental).

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Single parameter nonlinear EIDIP functions (recap)

E-space interdomain interaction potential (EIDIP) is a gravitational interaction energy imbalance produced potential (e.g., interaction energy of $[R] + [C] \neq [L]$, T-R figure) :

- Space contains isotropic energy (**E-space**), aka quantum vacuum, which can be warped into matter embedded with pairs of **contractive** and **expansive** gravitational potentials, named **matter warped E-space potential (MWEP, $P_M(r)$, B-R equations)**, with **non-zero-singularities at $[2]_\ell$** with the ℓ denote the natural unit of the **energy domain (E-domain)** where the MWEP operates;
- The **gravitational interaction energy imbalance** between MWEPs produces another potentials, name **E-space interdomain interaction potential (EIDIP)**: target-centric EIDIP = $([R]+[C])-[L]$ and reference-centric EIDIP = $([L]+[C])-[R]$;
- The short range EIDIP is **object-asymmetric** because of the interaction energy of $[R] \neq [L]$; however, the long-range EIDIPs are approximately **object-symmetric** because of the long-range interaction energy of $[R] \approx [L]$;
- The simplest two body interaction EIDIP is a **single parameter $T_c = \ell_t / \ell_f$** (aka interdomain transform coupling) **nonlinear function of distance** (B-L figure, next slide): $P_E(r_o; [T_c]) = 2\pi \iint \{P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t; [T_c]) \times \cos \theta\} d\theta dr_t$;
- MWEP transformations produce **entangled and complementary eXpansive and contractive pairs** of gravitational potentials with its own **energy domain (E-domain)** spatial units (**DSU, ℓ**): $[1]_{Dx\#} = [(32\pi)^\# c/2]_m$ for expansive **xE-MWEPs** and $[1]_{Dc\#} = [R_0/(32\pi)^\#]_m$ for contractive **cE-MWEPs**; where the $R_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1/(32\pi c)$ is a defined unit-less constant; the **symmetrical cE- and xE-MWEPs** also produce **symmetrical cE- and xE-EIDIP effects**.

$$P_E(r_o; [T_c]) = 2\pi \iint \{P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t; [T_c]) \times \cos \theta\} d\theta dr_t$$

$$P_M^t(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2T_c}{r}\right] \frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}, & r \geq [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \\ [T_c] \frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}, & r < [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \end{cases}$$

$$P_M^f(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r}\right] \frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}, & r \geq [2]_{\ell_f} \\ [1] \frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}, & r < [2]_{\ell_f} \end{cases}$$

EIDIP effects functions (recap)

The dynamic EIDIP effects inherit all the EIDIP's strange behaviors:

- The EIDIP and derived effects from dynamic interactions are **turbulent in short range** and **ruly in long-range**, e.g., $P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$ (B-L figure); some short-range EIDIP effects can even change directions and signs, e.g., the *irrotational* gradient-EIDIP effect $P_d \equiv d(P_E)/dr$ underlying the nuclear force (red curve, B-M figure) and the *rotational* angular-EIDIP $P_r \equiv rP_E$ and $P_r^\infty \equiv rP_E^\infty \propto cnst$ underlying the strong force (red curve, B-R figure) ;
- Although the eXpansive type EIDIP (aka xE-EIDIP) effects are neglectable in macro scales, some of them have long-range non-decaying (color confinement) behaviors and have been observed; e.g., xE-domain angular-EIDIP P_r underlying the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 sunward acceleration anomalies (red curve, B-R figure);
- The symmetrical contractive-expansive and distance dependent turbulent-ruly EIDIP effects in these **4 quadrants** can unified gravity with other fundamental-or-not and anomalous forces.
- Being unaware this connection, conventional models employ disparate models to describe the short- and long-range EIDIP effects induced phenomena, e.g., the SM describes the subatomic near-singular turbulent EIDIP effects (NSTEE), whereas the EM model describe the ruly long-range EIDIP effects.

Nuclear binding energy NBE-EEPT and NHTD

Nuclear binding energy (NBE) is produced by the internucleon Dc2-domain EIDIP: ([1].V.A)

- **P-NHTD:** EIDIP curve $BE_{ref} = [P_E \times [2H_{MC}^0 \times R_0^2 / (32\pi)]_{MeV/c^2} \times c^2]_{MeV}$ (purple lines, T-R figure) traces upper bound of experimental NBEs of the 2438 $A > 16$ nuclei listed in the AME2012 table (green dots); the insert figure shows the details of BE_{ref} curve and the periodic table elements (black dots);
- **P-NHTD:** With reference to the experimental NBEs of the 2438 $A > 16$ nuclei, their NBE deviation from the BE_{ref} is a **parabola function** (B-R figure), the main reason why the P_E based semi-empirical formula EPNBE-SEF have a lower **0.094** standard deviation than the **0.415** standard deviation of the [liquid-drop model Bethe-Weizsäcker NBE-SEF*](#);
- **P-NHTD:** The distance to mass number scalar $A = [r]_m / [R_u]_m$ with $R_u = [1/c^2]_m$ revealed the quantized **lower bound inter-particle distance (LBID)** unit; which is a paramount parameter to achieve the sustain accuracy of the EIDIP based nuclear charge radius (NCR) semi-empirical formula EPNCR-SEF shown in the next slide;
- **S-NHTD:** $H_{MC}^0 = [4\pi 10^4]_{MeV/c^2} = [125.664]_{GeV/c^2}$ is within the ATLAS and CMS's uncertainty limit; note that the $[2H_{MC}^0 \times R_0^2 / (32\pi)]_{MeV/c^2} \cong iMu = [(10^{-17} / R_0)^3 (32\pi)]_{MeV/c^2}$, the original internucleon [interaction defect mass unit](#) discovered prior to the 2012 Higgs boson discovery, with only 8.61×10^{-5} relative deviation between them.

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Light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs and NHTD

These EIDIP effect parameters: R_u , R_{SF}^{max} , and R_{NNP}^{max} , are the major part of light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs which produce NCRs matched the measurements: ([1].V.C)

- **P-NHTD:** EIDIP framework posited (2013) that **proton has a ridge core** $r_p = R_c^P + R_{SF}^{max} = [0.8419]_{fm}$, that mostly composed of projectile swing-by radius $R_{SF}^{max} = [0.707056]_{fm}$ (A & B, top figure), and it is projectile's radii, electronic R_c^e and muonic R_c^μ , determine the electronic and muonic proton NCRs; (**proton fermion core:** $R_c^P = (R_q + R_q^-)/2$, $R_q^- = R_q/(32\pi)$, $R_q = 24R_u$); the EIDIP framework's prediction that **proton has a ridge core** $r_p = [0.8419]_{fm}$ (2013) has been affirmed by the later measurement $[0.833(10)]_{fm}$ (2019*);
- **S-NHTD:** the **muonic proton SEF** $R_p^\mu = [0.842234]_{fm}$ compares with the measured muonic proton NCR $[0.84184(67)]_{fm}$;
- **S-NHTD:** the **electronic proton SEF** $R_p^e = [0.872816]_{fm}$ compares with the CODATA 2010 electronic proton NCR $[0.8775(51)]_{fm}$;
- **S-NHTD:** the **neutron SEF** $R_N = [-0.114695]_{fm}$ compares with the neutron NCR $[-0.1149(27)]_{fm}$ listed in the 2013 Atomic Data and Nuclear Data table;
- **S-NHTD:** the **deuteron SEF** $R_{De} = [2.141478]_{fm}$ compares with the CODATA 2010 Deuteron NCR $[2.1421(21)]_{fm}$;
- The **Helium-4 SEF** $R_{H4} = 1.680158]_{fm}$, almost half of it is from $R_{SF}^{max} \cong [0.707056]_{fm}$, only has a $[0.00608]_{fm}$ deviation from the CODATA 2010 Helium-4 NCR $[1.6755(28)]_{fm}$.

Name	Semi-empirical Formula (SEF)
Proton	$R_p^\mu = R_c^P + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^\mu$ (muonic) $R_p^e = R_c^P + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^e$ (electronic)
Neutron	$R_N = R_c^N - R_{SF}^{max}$
Deuteron	$R_{De} = R_{NP} + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^e$ with $R_{NP} = R_c^N + R_{NNP}^{max} + R_c^P$
Helium-4	$R_{H4} = k_{cr}(R_{NP} + R_q/2) + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^e$ with $k_{cr} = 0.612372$ is the tetrahedron circumsphere radius to edge ratio

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Nuclear charge radii EPNCR-SEF and NHTD

Nuclear charge radii (NCR) include these EIDIP effect radius revealed in other EEPTs: R_u , R_{SF}^{max} , and R_{NNP}^{max} : ([1].V.B)

- R_u : the quantized lower bound inter-particle distance, R_{SF}^{max} : the maximum **strong interaction** (SF) radius, and R_{NNP}^{max} : the maximum **nucleon-nucleon potential** (NNP) radius;
- **P-NHTD : accuracy of EPNCR-SEF**: With reference to those mass number ≥ 16 **885** nuclei NCR (blue dots, T-R figure;) listed in the ADND13 Table, **47.8%** of the EPNCR-SEF produced NCRs (red dots) are within the uncertainties vs. the **35.5%** of the SWNCR-SEF produced NCRs. The EPNCR-SEF's NCR deviation also yielded a $rms = [0.0199]_{fm}$ vs. the SWNCR-SEF's $[0.0218]_{fm}$ provided by Dr. Ning Wang on July 2013;
- **P-NHTD**: The gradient of the base line NCR $R_b = R_q\sqrt{A} + R_{oft}^b$ with $R_q = 24R_u$ (brown curve, T-R figure) and the **sub-shell adjustment** $3R_u$ (B-R figure shown the *pre-adjustment* deviations and the gap between horizontal dot-dashed lines is $3R_u$) are related to the quantized R_u ;
- The fitted $R_{oft}^b \cong [1.858]_{fm}$, 38% is from the swing by distance $R_{SF}^{max} \cong [0.707056]_{fm}$ between the projectile and nuclide, is only about 10% higher than the tetrahedron-form Helium-4 NCR listed in the 2013 Atomic Data and Nuclear Data (ADND13);
- **S-NHTD**: the NCR sub-shell adjustment $3R_u$ not only revealed that the heavy nuclei can have **multilayer shell structures** but also is the main reason that the EPNCR-SEF has **sustaining accuracy** over multiple datasets (Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables 2004 and 2013).

Interatomic covalent force (IACF) EEPT & NHTD

Interatomic gradient-EIDIP produced the Interatomic covalent force (IACF): ([1].V.A)

- **P-NHTD:** Gradient-EIDIP P_d based IACF curve $G_{PGA}^{IACF-tip1} = P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times M_{kg}^{IACF} / 24$ with the effective mass unit $M_{kg}^{IACF} = [1/(32\pi)^3]_{kg}$ (blue line, top figure) traces the empirical IACF mean (black) curve (tip-1)*;
- **P-NHTD:** Gradient-EIDIP P_d based IACF curve $G_{PGA}^{IACF-tip2} = P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times M_{kg}^{IACF} / 4$ (blue line, bottom figure) traces the empirical IACF mean (black) curve (tip-2)*;
- **P-NHTD:** the distance scalar for tip-1 $k_x^{tip1} = [4]_{Dc0} = [4R_0]_m$ is a harmonic Dc0-domain spatial unit (**Dc0-DSU**);
- **P-NHTD:** the distance scalar for tip-2 $k_x^{tip2} = [2]_{Dc0}$ is also a harmonic Dc0-DSU;
- **S-NHTD:** The IACF EEPTs affirm that underlying **Dc0-MWEPs**, aka macroscopic gravitational potentials, do have quantized non-zero-singularities at $[2]_{Dc0} = [2R_0]_m$, and that the macroscopic gravitational potentials have **gravitational coupling constant** $[2R_0]_m^3/s^2$ (about 99.43% of the 2014 CODATA gravitational constant value);
- The IACF-EEPTs have a $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ scalar term shared with other gradient-EIDIP based EEPTs.

Intermolecular van der Waals force EEPT & NHTD

Intermolecular gradient-EIDIP produced the Intermolecular interaction energy or van der Waals force (IMVF):

- **P-NHTD:** Gradient-EIDIP P_d based intermolecular van der Waals force (IMVF) curve $G_{PGA}^{IMVF} = P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times M_{kg}^{IAVF}$ (blue curve, right figure) traces the interaction energy of argon dimer curve (red curve)* with an effective mass unit $M_{kg}^{IAVF} = [1.275/(32\pi)^3]_{kg}$ and a distance scalar $k_x = [1.5]_{Dc0}$;
- **S-NHTD:** the IMVF-EEPT has revealed that the macroscopic Dc0-domain gravitational potentials (**Dc0-MWEP**) do have quantized non-zero-singularities;
- The IMVF-EEPT has a $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ scalar term shared with other gradient-EIDIP based EEPTs.

Newtonian gravitational constant EEPT & NHTD

Newtonian gravitational constant derived from measurements contain environmental and inter test objects EIDIP effects, i.e., not a constant: ([1].VI.B)

- It is a well-known fact that there are large deviations between Newtonian gravitational constant measurements; these Newtonian gravitational constant deviation (NGCD) can be explained by long-range ruly EIDIP effects between test objects and environment ([1].VI.B.1);
- **P-NHTD**: True **gravitational coupling constant** $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$: the IACF and IMVF EEPTs have revealed that the macroscopic gravitational potential have singularity unit of $[2]_{Dc0} = [2R_0]_m$ and an effective coupling constant $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ that covers **99.43%** of the 2014 CODATA recommended gravitational constant value $[6.67408(31) \times 10^{-11}]_{m^3/s^2}$;
- **P-NHTD**: The rest of 0.57% NGCD can be fill in by the EIDIP effect couplings; e.g., the long-range settle-to-constant irrotational interatomic Covalent force coupling is $G_{PGC}^{IACF} = r^2 G_{PGA}^{IACF} = [3.36716 \times 10^{-13}]_{Nm^2}$ (figure left) such that it reduces the **NGCD** from 0.57% to **0.07%**; other *rotational* and *irrotational* EIDIP effects couplings, environmental or between test objects, can further reduce the NGCD;
- **S-NHTD**: the NGCD-EEPT has mass unit of $[1]_{kg}$ which indicates that the NGCD-EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental; note that the $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ scalar term is shared with other gradient-EIDIP based EEPTs.

$$G_{PGC}^{NGCD} = [P_d^\infty 2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3]_N^{PGA} [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (R_0^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2} r^2$$

$$G_{PGA}^{NGCD} = [P_d \times [1]_{kg} \times 2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3]_N^{PGA}$$

$$k_x = [1]_{Dc0}$$

Bohr radius EEPT & NHTD

The measured Bohr radius is mostly composed of the most attractive radius of Dc0-domain angular-EIDIP R_{Bohr}^{max} : ([1].VII.B)

- The light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs has reveals that the major part of measured nuclear charge radius is the most attractive swing-by radius R_{SF}^{max} of the Dc2.5-domain angular-EIDIP;
- **P-NHTD**: the measured Bohr radius is also mostly composed of most attractive swing-by radius: $R_{Bohr}^{max} = [5.27747 \times 10^{-11}]_m$ of the Dc0-domain angular-EIDIP (blue curve, right figure, with the red vertical dashed line indicates the R_{Bohr}^{max}); which matches 99.73% of the CODATA Bohr Radius $[5.2917721067(12) \times 10^{-11}]_m$; the **0.27% relative deviation** from the CODATA Bohr Radius could represent the atom core and orbiting electron's radii;
- **P-NHTD**: The distance scalar $k_x = [1]_{Dc0} = [R_0]_m$ revealed the interatomic EIDIP effect Dc0-Pr underlying the Bohr radius measurements and affirmed that the Bohr radius EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental;
- **S-NHTD**: The underlying **Dc0-MWEPs** have quantized non-zero-singularities at $[2]_{Dc0} = [2R_0]_m$ such that the Bohr radius EEPTs affirm that the macroscopic gravitational potentials **do** have quantized non-zero-singularities at $[2]_{Dc0}$.

Strong force (SF) EEPT & NHTD

The subatomic roattional angular-EIDIP produces the strong force: ([1].VII.A)

- It is well-known that strong force has these strange behaviors: **asymptotic** (getting weaker as distance decreases) at short distances and **color-confinement** (settle-to-constant) after a limiting distance (about the size of a hadron, $\approx [0.9]_{fm}$) has been reached;
- P-NHTD**: Angular-EIDIP based strong force P_r -SF curve (blue curve, T-R figure) depicts the well-known strange behaviors of the strong force: asymptotic at short distances: $P_E^+ \propto r^1 \rightarrow P_r^+ = rP_E^+ \propto r^2$ and settle-to-constant at long distances: $P_E^\infty \propto r^{-1} \rightarrow P_r^\infty = rP_E^\infty \propto cnst$;
- P-NHTD**: With the distance scalar $k_x = [1]_{DC2.5}$, the P_r -SF curve depicts the color-confinement behavior after reaches the size of a hadron ($\approx [0.9]_{fm}$); the k_x is also shared with other subatomic EEPTs such that this P_r -SF EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental;
- S-NHTD**: the maximum attraction radius $R_{SF}^{max} = [0.707056]_{fm}$ (light brown area, B-R figure) are part of the accurate light and heavy EPNCR-SEFs;
- S-NHTD**: The long-range $G_{APA}^{SF} = [P_r^\infty \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times 2_{Dx2.5}^2]_N^{APA} = [10359]_N$ compares with the estimated confinement-SF strength $[9800]_N^*$.

Neutron-Neutron potential NNP-EEPT & NHTDs

The subatomic irrotational gradient-EIDIP produced the Neutron-neutron potential (NNP), aka residual nuclear force or strong nuclear force: ([1].VI.C)

- “This idea of a repulsive core in the strong nuclear force is something thrown around as this mythical thing that exists, but we don’t know how to get there, like this portal from another realm,” said Dr. Axel Schmidt, a postdoctoral researcher at MIT and George Washington University;
- **P-NHTD:** The subatomic Gradient-EIDIP P_d based neutron-neutron potential curve (blue line, T-R figure) depicts the repulsive core near origin and a highly attractive $[0.4 - 1.5]_{fm}$ region without hypothetic negative mass or YuKawa potential;
- **P-NHTD:** Gradient-EIDIP P_d based neutron-neutron potential curve $G_{PGP}^{NNP} = [P_d \times (M_{kg}^{NNP} c^2) \times 2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3]_{Nm}^{PGP}$ (purple dotted curve, B-R figure) with $M_{kg}^{NNP} = [1.014]_{eV/c^2} \cong [1]_{eV/c^2}$, compare with the [NNP curves from Monte Carlo Simulations of Lattice Quantum Chromodynamics](#);* the $M_{kg}^{NNP} \cong [1]_{eV/c^2}$ indicates that the NNP-EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental;
- **P-NHTD:** the P_d -NNP also has a DSU distance scalar $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ that shared with other subatomic EEPTs such that this NNP-EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental;
- **S-NHTD:** the maximum attraction radius $R_{NNP}^{max} \cong [0.673052]_{fm}$ (red vertical dashed line, T-R figure) are part of the accurate light and heavy EPNCR-SEFs.

Neutron charge distribution (NCD) EEPTs & NHTD

The neutron charge distribution experiments measured the Dc2.5-domain expulsive and attractive EIDIP effect couplings, not positive and negative charges ([1].VIII.A-B):

- **P-NHTD**: the quadratic EIDIP effect coupling $P_E P_d$ -NCD curve (light blue curve, T-R figure; $k_x = [1.87]_{Dc2.5}$) from the bi-group (projectile and three-quark groups) **few-body** interaction traces the aggregated empirical NCD mean curve (black curve); note that the $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ $P_E P_d$ -NCD curve (blue-dotted line, T-R figure) traces the ascending slope of the aggregated empirical NCD mean curve without shifting;
- **S-NHTD**: the simpler **two-body** interaction rP_r' -NCD curve (light blue curve, B-R figure), although having noticeable deviations between $[0.7 - 2]_{fm}$ region, approximately traces the aggregated empirical NCD mean curve (black curve), especially the minimum and maximum magnitude ratio of the aggregated NCD mean curve; the simpler rP_r' -NCD also has a DSU distance scalar $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ that shared with other subatomic EEPTs such that this NCD-EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental.

Proton charge distribution (PCD) EEPTs & NHTDs

The proton charge distribution experiments actually measured the Dc2.5-domain EIDIP effect couplings, not charges. ([1].VIII.C-D)

- **P-NHTD**: the quadratic EIDIP effect coupling P_E^2/r -PCD curve (blue curve, shifted by $[0.08]_{fm}$, $k_x = [1.765]_{Dc2.5}$, right figure) from the bi-group (projectile and three-quark groups) **few-body** interaction traces the aggregated empirical PCD mean curve (black curve);
- **S-NHTD**: the simpler **two-body** interaction P_E -NCD curve (blue-dotted line) approximately traces the shape, especially the ascending slope, of the aggregated empirical PCD mean curve (black curve); the simpler P_E -NCD also has a DSU distance scalar $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ that shared with other subatomic EEPTs such that this P_E -PCD EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental.

Anomalous Magnetic Moment EEPT & NHTDs

The quantum hadronic contributions to the “Anomalous” Magnetic Moment (AMM) of the Muon describes the NSTEE contributions, a type of OEIA; e.g.,

- **Hadronic light-by-light scattering (HLLS) contribution:** Photons possess MWEF such that the interaction between them produces EIDIP effects; from which the attractive and expulsive NSTEEs induced forces engender the photon antibunching ([1].X.D.9) and contribute to the HLLS;
- **Hadronic vacuum polarization (HVP) contribution:** The expulsive EIDIP effect in the NSTEE region (e.g., rP_r' , ([1].Fig.70) can produce the hadron jets and virtual particle-antiparticle pair, aka HVP;
- **P-NHTD:** The EIDIP effect $P_E^2/r \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 2 \times 10^{-15}$ with distance scalar $2.5_{DC2.5} \times 10^{-15}$ quark **connected vector correlator (CVC)** curve (blue, T-R figure) approximately traces the scaled **strange** quark CVC curve (blue dot-line, T-R figure reproduced from Fig.1 of [*1]);
- **P-NHTD:** The EIDIP effect $P_d \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 1.5 \times 10^{-18}$ curve (blue curve, B-R figure) approximately traces the scaled quark **disconnected correlation function (DCF)** curve of the electromagnetic current computed at the physical pion mass (B-R figure, reproduced from Fig.3 of [*1]);
- **P-NHTD:** With the distance scalar $k_x = [2]_{DC2.5}$, the P_d -DCF curve can trace the empirical quark DCF is uncanny.

Section 2

*1 <https://www.gauss-centre.eu/results/elementaryparticlephysics/article/hadronic-contributions-to-the-anomalous-magnetic-moment-of-the-muon-from-lattice-qcd/>;

*2 <http://arxiv.org/pdf/0805.2462v2.pdf>;

Effective couplings: ERC, ESC, EMC, and EEC EEPTs

The subatomic interaction between the swing-by projectiles and targets can produce an composite EIDIP effect $rP'_r = P_d r^2 + P_r$ composed of a rotational component P_r and an irrotational component $P_d r^2$: ([1].VIII.E)

- **P-NHTD:** With a distance scalar $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$, the short-range (NSTEE region) rotational P_r based effective strong coupling (**ESC**) (red curve, T-R figure, blue curve, B-R figure) traces the QCD based ECS (B-R figure);
- **P-NHTD:** The short-range (NSTEE region) irrotational $P_d r^2$ based effective residual strong coupling (**ERC**) (green curve, T-R figure) is the coupling of the P_d -NNP curve that traces the neutron-neutron potential (NNP) or residual strong force curve;
- **P-NHTD:** the long-rang $[P_d^\infty r^2 \times H_{kg}^0 \times 4/(32\pi)^{2.5}]_{Nm^2}^{PGC}$ effective electrostatic coupling (**EEC**) magnitude (green curve, T-R figure) compares with the conventional $k_{EEC} \equiv [k_e e^2]_{Nm^2}$ with 4.43% relative deviation; and the $(32\pi)^{2.5}$ term reveals its Dc2.5-domain origin indicates that this $P_d^\infty r^2$ -EEC EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental;
- **P-NHTD:** the long-rang $[P_r^\infty \times H_{kg}^0 \times 4/(32\pi)^{2.5}]_{Nm^2}^{APC}$ effective magnetic coupling (**EMC**) magnitude (red curve) compares with the conventional $k_{EMC} \equiv \mu_0 e^2 c^2 / 4\pi = [\alpha \hbar c]_{Nm^2}$ with 4.43% relative deviation.

Composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing effects

Why the strong interaction, although non-decaying in long-range, yet it has very short interaction range? ([1].VIII.E.5)

- Some EIDIP effects can be neutralized by other EIDIP effects in very short distance; e.g., the combinations of the rotational P_r -ESC (red curve, T-R figure) and the irrotational $P_d r^2$ -ERC produce the $rP_r' \propto r^{-1}$ (blue curve, T-R figure) which has strong expulsive (positive) in the NSTEE region yet reduced to zero in short distance: long-range $rP_r' \propto r^{-1}$ (B-R figure), aka the long-range composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing effects (LCEN);
- **Y-NHTD: Strange strong interaction's long-range non-decaying strength yet short interaction range:** apart from angular EIDIP can explain the asymptotic and color confinement behaviors shown in SF-EEPT, the long-range composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing effects can explain SF's short interaction range. E.g., the effective strong coupling P_r -ESC (red curve, B-L figure) can be neutralized by the effective residual strong coupling $P_d r^2$ -ERC (green curve, B-L figure) such that the composite of which produced EIDIP effect $rP_r' = P_d r^2 + P_r$ (blue curve, B-R figure) reduces to zero in very short range;
- With high enough energy, the expulsive region of the EIDIP effect rP_r' (positive region of blue curve, T-R figure) can produce **hadron jets**; whereas the xE-domain counterpart can induce **astrophysical jets**.

Pioneer Sun-Ward Acceleration Anomaly EEPT

The interplanetary Dx2-domain angulare-EIDIP produced the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 sunward acceleration anomalies (PSAA) ([1].VII.C):

- **P-NHTD:** The Dx2-domain angular-EIDIP based P_r -PSAA curve (blue curve, T-R figure) traces *both* the steep-ascending and slow-descending segments of Pioneer 10/11 sunward acceleration [empirical data](#)*1 (black dots, right figure);
- **P-NHTD:** the distance scalar $k_x = [1]_{Dx2} = [(32\pi)^2 c/2]_m$ revealed the Dx2- P_r underlys the PSAA, and that the PSAA-EEPT is unlikely to be coincidental;
- Note that the P_r -PSAA curve's magnitude formula: $[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_{\odot} \times (2_{Dc2}^2) \times 1_{Dx2}]_N^{APA}$ contains a complementary E-domain terms 2_{Dc2}^2 as the 2_{Dx25}^2 of the strong force SF-EEPT magnitude formula: $[P_r^{\infty} \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times (2_{Dx25}^2)]_N^{APA}$;
- Note that the thermal recoil forces (TRF) PSAA model put forth by [Slava et al. 2012](#)*2 is not the right model; this is because 1) the slow *descending* TRF cannot explain the newer Pioneer 11's *ascending* data; 2) based on figure 4 of the paper (reproduced in B-R figure), the estimated *Jaccard similarity coefficient* between the TRF model data and Doppler residual empirical data is approximately 20% which indicates *inequality* between the TRF model and empirical data.

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*1:<http://arxiv.org/pdf/gr-qc/0507052v2.pdf>; *2: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2507>

Milky Way rotation curve CMWRC-EEPT & NHTDs

The Dx5-domain composite EIDIP effects induced “dark” forces, not dark matter, produced the Milky Way rotation curves (MWRC) ([1].VIII.F):

- **P-NHTD:** With a simplified radial-quadratic (RQ) galactic disk mass model $M_{kg}^{RQ} = M_{kg}^{ISO} (r^2 / 8_{kpc}^2)$, the quadratic EIDIP effect P_E^2 / r induced centripetal force (OCF) (blue line, B-L figure) and gravity-OCF (green line B-L figure) combo produced **QG-MWRC** curve (blue line, R-T figure; red-dashed line, B-L figure) can trace the observed MW RVs (CMWRC)*1 (open circles and squares, R-T figure);
- **Y-NHTD:** The EIDIP effect origin centripetal force (OCF) to gravity-OCF ratios k_E change the gradient of the MWRC’s turnover segment (blue, green, and red curves, B-L figure) such that they can be used fit other galaxies’ rotation curves; e.g., Fig 1 of [Aneta Wojnar, 2018]*2 (reproduced in B-R figure);
- **S-NHTD:** QG-MWRC’s $k_x = [4]_{Dx5}$ indicates the Dx5-EIDIP effects underlying the MWRC are faster than light $[4]_{Dx5/s} = [2(32\pi)^5 c]_{m/s} \approx [2 \times 10^{10} c]_{m/s}$, the observed faster-than-light gravity speed. (arxiv.org/abs/gr-qc/9909087).

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EIDIP effect phenomena test (EEPT) and Null hypothesis test node (NHTD)

RAVE-DR2 MWRC EEPTs & NHTDs

The EIDIP effects underlying the RAVE-DR2 MWRC EEPTs are dependent on the Milky Way mass model: QM: radial-quadratic, LM: radial-linear, CM: effective center, and the galactic radius type: spherical SgV_o and cylindrical CgV_o rotational velocities.*

- **P-NHTD**: the $Dx5-P_r'$ based **AG-MWRC** ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line) traces the RAVE-DR2 MW stars' cylindrical ortho-radial RV (color dots), radial bin-average absolute (RBAA)- CgV_o (magenta line) along cylindrical galactic radius (T-R fig.) ([1].VIII.G.2);
- **S-NHTD**: the $Dx5-P_r$ based **PG-MWRC** ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line) traces the RAVE-DR2 cylindrical ortho-radial (color dots), RBAA- CgV_o (LMWRC, magenta line) along cylindrical galactic radius (B-R fig.) ([1].Appendix.V.2);
- Milky Way mass models: Radial-quadratic $M_{kg}^{RQ} = M_{kg}^{ISO} (r^2 / 8_{kpc}^2)$; Radial-linear mass model $M_{kg}^{RL} = (M_{kg}^{ISO} / 40) (r / 8_{kpc})$; $M_{kg}^{EP} = M_{kg}^{ISO}$; $M_{kg}^{ISO} \cong 1.11 M_{kg}^{sta}$, $M_{kg}^{sta} = 6.43 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ as the upper bound of estimated.

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* $CgV_o = \vec{V}_{\phi}$ and $SgV_o = \vec{V}_{\theta} + \vec{V}_{\phi}$, $V_{\theta} = -V_{\rho} \sin \theta + V_z \cos \theta$ with θ as stars' galactic inclination angle, and V_{ρ} and V_z as stars' cylindrical radial and Z velocities

RAVE-DR2 Milky Way EEPTs & NHTD (continue)

- **P-NHTD**: the $Dx5-P_E^2/r$ based **QG-MWRC** ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line, T-R figure) traces the RAVE-DR2 MW stars' spherical ortho-radial RV (SgV_o , color dots), radial bin-averaged absolute RBAA- SgV_o (magenta line) along spherical galactic radius; ([1].VIII.G.1)
- **P-NHTD**: the $Dx5-rP_r'$ based **SG-MWRC** ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line, T-R figure) traces the RAVE-DR2 MW stars' cylindrical ortho-radial RV (color dots), radial bin-averaged absolute RBAA- CgV_o (magenta line) along cylindrical galactic radius; ([1].VIII.G.2)
- **P-NHTD**: These MWRC-EEPTs share the same harmonic $Dx5$ -domain spatial unit ($Dx5$ -DSU) distance scalar $k_x = [4]_{Dx5}$.

MWRC Model	Galactic radius type	Rotational velocity type	Mass model	EIDIP effect
QG	Spherical	SgV_o	RQ	P_E^2/r
AG	Cylindrical	CgV_o	RL	P_r'
SG	Cylindrical	CgV_o	RL	rP_r'
PG	Cylindrical	CgV_o	CM	P_r

MWRC dark matter Y-EEPT & Y-NHTD

The EIDIP effect induced dark forces (unknown to Newtonian gravity), not dark matter, produced the “anomalous” MWRC.

- **Y-EEPT:** Dark matter is a type of *omitting EIDIP effect induced artifacts (OEIA)*: Because gravity strength decreases with inverse distance square whereas some of the expansive astronomical EIDIP effects are non-decaying (e.g., $P_r^\infty \propto r^0$, blue curve, T-R figure), these astronomical non-decaying EIDIP effects would surpass Newton gravity (green line, T-R figure) at some astronomical distance and become dominant ([1].VII.C.2). Hence, the Keplerian predictions, which did not account for the dominating EIDIP effects produced “dark” forces, would require much higher than observable mass, the **dark matter**, to explain the dark forces;
- **Y-NHTD:** With a simplified radial-quadratic (RQ) galactic disk mass model $M_{kg}^{RQ} = M_{kg}^{ISO} (r^2/8_{kpc}^2)$, the quadratic EIDIP effect P_E^2/r induced centripetal force (OCF) (blue line, B-R figure) can be two orders of magnitude higher than the gravity-OCF (green line) in the blue-dashed box region; because EIDIP effects are beyond the Newtonian limit and can not be eliminate by relativistic adjustments such that the conventional models require the hypothetic **dark matter** gravity-OCF to fill in the EIDIP effect P_E^2/r -OCFs ([1].VIII.G.4);
- The Milky Way’s dark halo appears to extend out to at least 300,000 light years*, about 92 kpc, which aligned with the EIDIP dominated region shown in B-R figure.

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* <https://astronomy.swin.edu.au/cosmos/D/dark+halo>

Precession of Mercury and bending of light Y-EEPT

The “new” field theory*, $A \approx -\alpha/r$, approximately describes the long-range ruly xE-EIDIP effects $P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$.

- The long-range EIDIP effects are ruly that they can be approximated by the inversed distance function, $P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$ ([1].III.A, equation 26);
- **Y-NHTD**: A “new” field theory* formulation and a space-time adjustment that predict the same precession of Mercury and the same bending of light as **general relativity**; the field theory is based on a fragment of energy, defined as $A \approx -\alpha/r$ where α is intensity and r is the distance function (PHYSICS ESSAYS 33, 4 (2020)); these findings, although still an approximated result because they did not account for the full ranges of the NSTEEs, indicated that xE-EIDIP effects can replace the relativistic adjustments and explain the precession of Mercury and bending of light;
- The Perihelion (closest) and Aphelion (furthest) radius of Mercury from Sun is $r_a = [4.6002e10]_m$ and $r_p = [6.982e10]_m$, or $r_a = [0.03]_{Dx2} = [3.05]_{Dx1} = [306.89]_{Dx0}$ and $r_p = [0.046]_{Dx2} = [4.63]_{Dx1} = [465.33]_{Dx0}$; which put Mercury’s orbit in the *asymptotic* region Dx2-EIDIP effects, and ruly long-range Dx0-EIDIP effects $P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$ from Sun;
- Refer to the EIDIP functions in the asymptotic region Dx2-EIDIP effects near $[0.03]_{Dx2}$ are neglectable, and the lower order Dx0 and Dx1-EIDIP effects are in the long-range ruly region such that the combination of which can be approximated by $P_E \propto 1/r$, or $A \approx -\alpha/r$, as expected (with the magnitude scalar α as in the 10+ EEPTs).

$$P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$$

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New dark matter map reveals cosmic mystery

New dark matter map reveals the matter isn't as clumpy as expected – there are hints that it is smoother; which could imply that there's something wrong with Einstein's theory of relativity.

- The new dark matter map are generated by measuring the shape shearing of the background galaxies from light bending predicted by the GR; with the help of including the motion of galaxies, their radial peculiar velocities, in addition to their distribution drastically enhanced the quality of the map and allowed us to see these details;
- A “new” field theory* formulation and a space-time adjustment that predict the same precession of Mercury and bending of light the same as general relativity; The “new” field theory*, $A \approx -\alpha/r$, approximately describes the long-range xE-EIDIP effects $P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$; although the field theory dose not account for the turbulent EIDIP effects in the NSTEE region, their finding does indicates that those “relativistic” astronomical phenomena are those noticeable beyond-Newtonian limit EIDIP effects; GR's monochronic relativistic adjustments can not describe those nondecaying EIDIP effects (e.g., $P_r^\infty \propto r^0$);

- **Y-NHTD:** As that the expulsive EIDIP effects between two supergalactic structures or galaxy groups, the expulsive EIDIP effects can also affect radial peculiar velocities of galaxies;
- However, GR's monochronic relativistic adjustments can not describe the turbulent (sign changing, direction changing) xE-domain EIDIP effects near singularity (aka NSTEE region).

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Galactic MW turnover ring Y-EEPT & Y-NHTD

The EIDIP effects underlying the “anomalous” MWRC also included galactic turnover rings.

- **Y-NHTD**: the Dx5-EIDIP effect P_r' -OCF (red-dotted line, B-L figure) can also overpower the gravity-OCF (green line) such that the combined OCF (red dotted line) induced negative gravitational force (NGF) region (red dashed box) and gravitational force ripple (GFR) region (blue dashed box); the MW turnover galactic rings were observed near the acme of MW rotation curve where these gravitational force ripples reside; i.e., the EIDIP effects induced GRFs can cause the galactic turnover ring formations ([1].VIII.G.4).

Expulsive EIDIP effects Y-EEPTs and Y-NHTDs

All matter and energy entities possess MWEPs regardless their size such that the expulsive composite EIDIP effects between them can eject materials or keep them apart.

- The 10+ EEPTs have shown that EIDIP effects can describe the interactions of these elementary and composite particles: quark, electron, nucleon, and atom to astronomical objects: Sun and Milky Way, without involving these massless force-carrying bosons: photon, gluon, and hypothetical graviton and astronomic bosons;
- **Y-NHTD: Astrophysical jets:** The astronomical near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (magenta box region, R-T figure) could induce astrophysical jets; e.g., the galactic range xE-domain rP_r' (blue curves, R-T and R-B figures) and rP_d (green curve) (positive: repulsive, negative: attractive) ([1].X.D.4);
- **Y-NHTD: hadron jets:** the subatomic (contractive) expulsive EIDIP effects can explain the hadron jets ([1].X.D.4);
- **Y-NHTD: Photon antibunching:** Photons possess MWEPs such that the expulsive EIDIP effects between them can keep them apart; ([1].X.D.9)
- **Y-NHTD: Accelerating expansion of the universe:** the interaction between super-galactic groups produces super-galactic composite xE-EIDIP effects; of which the expulsive effects can explain the observed accelerating expansion of the universe ([1].X.D.7).

Neutron EDM problem & proton spin crisis Y-EEPTs

Both the neutron electric dipole moment (EDM) problem and the proton spin crisis are likely OEIAs ([1].X.D.13).

- The PCD and NCD EEPTs have revealed that the measured PCDs and NCDs are distance dependent EIDIP effects **coupling** rather than **charges** distributions (e.g., rP_r' -NCD, T-L figure); i.e., there are no conventional sense positive and negative charges distributed inside protons and neutrons;
- The long-range ruly fields used by the measurements have near-zero effects in changing the behaviors of the distance-dependent near-singularity-turbulent-EIDIP-effects;
- **Y-NHTD*2**: Protons spin and neutron EDM measurements uses the long-range ruly EM fields that have little effects on the near-singularity-turbulent-EIDIP-effects to decipher (through some measurable change) the near-singularity-turbulent-EIDIP-effects; i.e., the distance-dependent NSTEEs cannot be altered much in the long-range ruly regions where the measurements take place; hence, the neutron EDM problem and proton spin crisis;
- Neutron “charge” distribution curve (rP_r' -NCD, $rP_r' = P_d r^2 + P_r$, light blue curve, T-L figure) is composed of an irrotational $P_d r^2$ -ERC curve (blue line, B-L figure) and a rotational P_r -ESC curve (green line) and proton “charge” distribution P_E^2/r -curve (red line, scaled for clarity); blue vertical dashed line: neutron core radius, magenta dashed line: proton core radius.

Near earth flyby anomalies (NEFA) Y-EEPTs

The anomalous accelerations of near earth flybys are produced by the Dx0-EIDIP effects between the flybys and Moon (mostly) or earth (minor) ([1].X.D.22).

- At minimum altitude between the NEAR-flyby and earth (red vertical dashed line, figure right), the angular-EIDIP P_r induced acceleration G_{APA} on the NEAR-flyby is about 600 times weaker than the NEAR-flyby and Moon (between green and blue vertical dashed lines); i.e., the interactions between the flybys and the Moon can play a dominant role in the NEFAs; accounting for Earth and Moon mass-ratio of about 81.3, the Moon- to Earth-OCFs ratio drops to about 7.3; note that these estimates neither account for the effects of the NEAR-flyby's dynamics (e.g., rotational and inclination angles) on the rotational G_{APA} nor other irrotational EIDIP effects;
- **Y-NHTD**: i.e., at the NEAR-flyby's minimum altitude position, ignoring the inclination angle effect, the Moon-OCF is the dominant source;
- **Y-NHTD**: the estimated single digit ratio between the Moon-OCF to Earth-OCF of the NEAR-flyby case opens the door to explain other NEFAs (e.g., the MESSENGER NEFA) that experienced very low anomalous acceleration.

Gravity wave (GW) Y-EEPTs & Y-NHTD

The observed gravity wave (GW) beat frequency amplitude (BFA) have both down- and up-sweep patterns:

- Although some GW strains' down-sweep BFA patterns more obvious than others, the [GW150914 strains](#)^{*1}: H1 (Hanford, (B-L fig), L1 (Livingston, B-M fig) ([1].X.D.21), and the [GW190521 strains](#)^{*2}: H1 (L-T fig), L1 (L-M fig), and V1 (L-B fig) all have both down-sweep and up-sweep beat frequency amplitude (BFA) patterns;
- **Y-NHTD** The astronomical range EIDIP effect $rP'_{r[D]}$ -GW curves (orange or purple dashed curves) can trace the BFA patterns of GW150914-strains:H1 (B-L fig.), L1 (B-M fig.), and GW190521 strains: H1 (L-T), L1 (L-M), and V1(L-B);
- Note that in the Fig. 72 of [1], the $rP'_{r[D]}$ -GW curve was plotted in linear scales whereas the [GW150914 strains](#) BFA plots were plotted in log2 scales. The $rP'_{r[D]}$ -GW curve in the B-R figure is plotted in log2 scale to match the [GW150914 strains](#) BFA plot.

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*1: <https://physics.aps.org/featured-article-pdf/10.1103/PhysRevLett.116.061102> *2: https://www.gw-openscience.org/eventapi/html/03_Discovery_Papers/GW190521/v1/

EIDIP effect phenomena test (EEPT) and Null hypothesis test node (NHTD)

EEPT magnitude formula summary table

EEPT name	Dist.	Magnitude formula	IDTC (T_c)
Pioneer anomaly (PSAA):	[1] _{Dx2}	$[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_{\odot} \times (2_{Dc2}^2) \times 1_{Dx2}]_N^{APA}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Milky Way rotation curve (PG-MWRC):	[4] _{Dx5}	$[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_{kg}^{EP} \times (2_{Dc2}^2) \times 4 \times k'_M]_N \rightarrow k'_M \approx 1$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Bohr Radius:	[1] _{Dc0}	$[P_r]_{Dc0}$	(32π)
Strong force (SF)	[1] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_r \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times (2_{Dx2.5}^2)]_N^{APA}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Effective strong coupling (ESC)	[1] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_r]_{Dc2.5}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Effective magnetic coupling (EMC)	[1] _{Dc2.5}	$[(P_r^{\infty}/r^2) \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{APA} \times [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2}^{r^2}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Interatomic covalent force (IACF-tip1)	[4] _{Dc0}	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times [1/(32\pi)^3]_{kg}^{IACF}/24]_N^{PGA}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Interatomic covalent force (IACFtip-2)	[2] _{Dc0}	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times [1/(32\pi)^3]_{kg}^{IACF}/4]_N^{PGA}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Intermolecular van der Waals force (IMVF)	[1.5] _{Dc0}	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times [1/(32\pi)^3]_{kg}^{IACF}] \times 2.55_N^{PGA}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Newtonian G constant deviation (NGCD)	[1] _{Dc0}	$[P_d^{\infty} \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times [1]_{kg}^{NGCD}]_N^{PGA} [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2}^{r^2}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Effective residual strong coupling (ERC)	[1] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{PGA} [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2}^{r^2}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Effective electrostatic coupling (EEC)	[1] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_d^{\infty} \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{PGA} [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2}^{r^2}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Neutron-neutron potential (NNP)	[1] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times (M_{kg}^{NNP} c^2)]_N^{PGP}; M_{kg}^{NNP} \rightarrow [1]_{eV/c^2};$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Quark disconnected correlation function (DCF)	[2] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_d \times 1.5(H_{Mc}^0 \times 10^{-9})^2] \approx [P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times (M_{kg}^{NNP} c^2) \times 10^{-9}]$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Nuclear binding energy (NBE)	$A \times R_u$	$[P_E \times 2H_{Mc}^0 / (32\pi)^3]_{MeV}^{BEref}$ or $[P_E \times H_{kg}^0 R_0^2 \times 1_{Dc2}]_{Nm}^{BEref}$	(32π)
Neutron charge distribution (rP_r' -NCD):	[1] _{Dc2.5}	$[rP_r' \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 5.3 \times 10^{-13}]_{fm^{-1}}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Milky Way rotation curve (SG-MWRC)	[4] _{Dx5}	$[rP_r' \times (H_{kg}^0)^2 \times M_{kg}^{RL} \times 5.25 \times k'_M]_N; M_{kg}^{RL} \cong (M_{kg}^{ISO}/40)(r/8_{kpc})$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Milky Way rotation curve (AG-MWRC)	[4] _{Dx5}	$[P_r' \times (H_{kg}^0)^2 \times M_{kg}^{RQ} \times 5.25 \times k'_M]_N; M_{kg}^{RQ} = M_{kg}^{ISO}(r^2/8_{kpc}^2)$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Neutron charge distribution ($P_E P_d$ -NCD)	[1.87] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_E P_d \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 2 \times 10^{-14}]_{fm^{-1}}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Proton charge distribution (P_E^2/r -PCD)	[1.77] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_E^2/r \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 2 \times 10^{-13}]_{fm^{-1}}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Strange-quark connected correlator (CVC)	[2.5] _{Dc2.5}	$[P_E^2/r \times (H_{kg}^0)^2 \times 2 \times 10^{-15}]$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Milky Way rotation curve (QG-MWRC, CMWRC)	[4] _{Dx5}	$[P_E^2/r \times (H_{kg}^0)^2 \times M_{kg}^{RQ} \times 2.35 \times k'_M]_N$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$

Additional primary NHTDs

The interdomain coupling T_c can not only affects the shaped of EIDIP effect functions, but also affects the magnitude of which (B-L figure).

- **P-NHTD*18:** These 18 EEPTs' T_c are primary NHTDs because it is uncanny that these EEPTs can cover such a wide range of phenomena, from subatomic to astronomic, with only two T_c values: $(32\pi)^{1/4}$ and 32π ; with the 36 presented in prior slides, it comes to **54 P-NHTDs total**;
- **P-NHTD*10:** (have been counted in prior slides) The 10 EEPTs in the NSTEE region where the distance scalar are sensitive (e.g., IACF-EEPT, B-R figure) and have integer DSU distance scalars are uncanny enough to be assigned as primary NHTDs; this is because that the single shaping-parameter T_c nonlinear EIDIP functions can be distance scaled with DSUs to fit those complex physical phenomena is **uncanny**.

EEPT name	Distance	IDTC (T_c)
Pioneer anomaly (PSAA)	[1] _{DCx2} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Milky Way rotation curve (PG-MWRC)	[4] _{DCx5} &P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ &P
Bohr Radius	[1] _{DC0} #P	(32π) #P
Strong force (SF)	[1] _{DC2.5} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Effective strong coupling (ESC)	[1] _{DC2.5} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Effective magnetic coupling (EMC)	[1] _{DC2.5} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Interatomic covalent force (IACF-tip1)	[4] _{DC0} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Interatomic covalent force (IACFtip-2)	[2] _{DC0} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ &P
Intermolecular van der Waals force (IMVF)	[1.5] _{DC0}	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Newtonian G constant deviation (NGCD)	[1] _{DC0} &P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Effective residual strong coupling (ERC)	[1] _{DC2.5} &P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Effective electrostatic coupling (EEC)	[1] _{DC2.5} &P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Neutron-neutron potential (NNP)	[1] _{DC2.5} &P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Quark disconnected correlation function	[2] _{DC2.5} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Nuclear binding energy (NBE)	$A \times R_u$ #P	(32π) #P
Neutron charge distribution (rP_r' -NCD)	[1] _{DC2.5} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ &P
Milky Way rotation curve (rP_r' -SG-MWRC)	[4] _{DCx5} &P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ &P
Milky Way rotation curve (P_r' -AG-MWRC)	[4] _{DCx5} &P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Neutron charge distribution ($P_E P_q$ -NCD)	[1.765] _{DC2.5}	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Proton charge distribution (P_E^2/r -PCD)	[1.87] _{DC2.5}	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Strange-quark connected correlator (CVC)	[2.5] _{DC2.5}	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P
Milky Way rotation curve (P_E^2/r -CMWRC)	[4] _{DCx5} #P	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #P

Additional inter-EEPT secondary NHTDs

These uncanny inter-EEPTs elements can be used as additional primary and secondary NHTDs:

- **S-NHTD:** The NBE EEPT magnitude formula revealed the relationship between the internucleon EIDIP and the Higgs-boson-like mass H_{Mc}^0 that is comparable to the ATLAS and CMS measurements; these Higgs-boson-like masses, H_{kg}^0 and H_{Mc}^0 , not only appear throughout the 10+ EEPTs' magnitude formulas but also simplify them to reveal the connections between the EEPTs;
- **S-NHTD:** the same type of EIDIP effect $\mathbf{rP}_{r'}$ underlying the **SG-MWRC** EEPT (B-L figure) and the neutron charge distribution (NCD) $\mathbf{rP}_{r'}$ -**NCD** EEPT;
- **S-NHTD:** the same type of EIDIP effect $\mathbf{P}_E^2/\mathbf{r}$ underlying the **QG-MWRC** EEPT (T-L figure) and the proton charge distribution $\mathbf{P}_E^2/\mathbf{r}$ -**PCD** EEPT;
- **S-NHTD:** **Dx5-P_r** based **PG-MWRC** and **Dx2-P_r** based **PSAA** EEPTs shared the same underlying angular-EIDIP effects;
- **S-NHTD:** Both the **P_r** based EEPTs: **Dx2-domain PSAA** and **Dc2.5-domain strong force (SF) magnitude formula** contains complementary E-domain terms 2_{Dc2}^2 (PSAA) and 2_{Dx25}^2 (SF);
- **S-NHTD:** The ESC, NCD, EEC, and EMC EEPTs reveal the intimate relationship between the EIDIP effects and residual-strong, strong, electrostatic, and magnetic couplings that described by **disparate** conventional models;
- **S-NHTD:** The EEC EEPT reveals the relationship between the irrotational $P_d^\infty r^2$ and $k_e e^2$; whereas the EMC EEPT reveals the relationship between the rotational P_r^∞ , and the fine structure α and reduced Planck \hbar constants;
- **S-NHTD:** The EEC and EMC magnitude formulas contain the $2_{Dc2.5}$ whereas the SF magnitude formula contains the complementary $2_{Dx2.5}$; these terms reflect their Dc2.5 origin;
- **S-NHTD:** The magnitude formulas: NNP $[P_d \times H_{Mc}^0 c^2 R_0^2]_{\text{MeV}}$ ([1].equ.57) and NBE $[P_E^{ita} \times 2 \times H_{Mc}^0 c^2 R_0^2]_{\text{MeV}}$ ([1].equ.45) share the term $H_{Mc}^0 c^2 R_0^2$;
- **S-NHTD:** The magnitude formulas of these gradient-EIDIP EEPTs: NNP, NGCD, EEC, EMC, IMVF, and IACF are **isomorphic** and have a **shared $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ term**;
- Including the **17 S-NHTDs** (excluding the **15 Y-NHTDs**) presented in prior slides, it comes to total of **27 S-NHTDs**.

In a nut shell

The EIDIP framework is built on these discoveries:

- Space contains isotropic energy (E-space), AND it is related to the **speed of light** and the true gravitational coupling constant;
- E-space can be warped into matter that can possess pairs of contractive and expansive gravitational potentials, named matter warped E-space potential (MWEP), with complementary non-zero-singularities (red-dashed circles, T-R figure) and energy domains (E-domain) because of the energy conservation law;
- MWEPs viewed from different E-domain have discontinuity-singularities because of their E-domain spatial unit (DSU) ratio (R_m^t/R_m^f , T-R figure);
- The **gravitational interaction energy imbalance** ($[R] \neq [L]$, T-R figure) produces an object-asymmetric potentials, name **E-space interdomain interaction potential (EIDIP)**: target-centric EIDIP = $[R]+[C]-[L]$ and reference-centric EIDIP= $[L]+[C]-[R]$; the long-range EIDIPs are **object-symmetric** because of the long-range $[R] \approx [L]$;
- The simplest two body interaction EIDIP is a **single parameter T_c nonlinear function of distance**: $P_E(r_o; [T_c]) = 2\pi \iint \{P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t; [T_c]) \times \cos \theta\} d\theta dr_t$; i.e., the T_c is the only parameter affects the shape of EIDIP function (B-R figure);
- The EIIDP and derived effects are turbulent in short range and ruly in long-range ($P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$, B-R figure); some short-range EIDIP effects can some can even change signs; e.g., gradient-EIDIP effect $d(P_E)/dr$ underlying the nuclear force;
- Although the expansive type EIDIP effects are neglectable in macro scales, some have long-range non-decaying behaviors (e.g., $rP_E^\infty \propto cnst$) such that they have been observed and partially modeled, e.g., precession of Mercury;
- Being unaware this connection, conventional physics employs disparate models to describe the short- and long-range EIDIP effects induced phenomena;
- The **contractive-expansive** and **turbulent-ruly** EIDIP effects can unify gravity with other fundamental-or-not and anomalous forces.

$$P_E(r_o; [T_c]) = 2\pi \iint \{P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t; [T_c]) \times \cos \theta\} d\theta dr_t$$

Vacuum energy and paired gravitational potentials

Energy space, pairs of complementary contractive-expansive gravitational potentials MWEPs, and energy domains (E-domain).

- **E-space:** Vacuum is an isotropic energy-space; of which the membrane tension $[R_0^2]_{m^2/s^4}^{IEMT}$ is related to the **speed of light c** and the **gravitational coupling constant** $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ which equals 99.43% of the 2014 CODATA-recommended gravitational constant value, where the $R_0 \stackrel{def}{=} 1/(32\pi c)$ is a defined unit-less constant, one of two first principle equations of the EIDIP framework;
- **MWEP transformation:** An isotropic E-space membrane can ripple because of internal or external dynamics; if the disturbance is large enough, it can warp the E-space membrane into matter (e.g., quark) with a spherical energy structure composed of a pair of complementary contractive and expansive gravitational potentials, named matter warped E-space potential (**MWEP**) because of the **energy conservation law**: $[1^2]_{m^2} = [(32\pi R_0) \times c]_{m^2}$ (T-R figure), or $[R_0^2]_{m^2/s^4}^{IEMT} [1^2]_{m^2} = [4\pi(2R_0)^2]_{m^2} \times [2R_0]_{m/s^2}^{EXTRT} \times [c]_{m/s^2}^{ECTRT}$ (B-R figure);
- **Complementary E-domain pair:** Because the disturbance energy can have multiple Fourier frequencies and the **energy conservation law**, the MWEP transformations produced elementary particles can possess pairs of MWEPs that operate in **complementary energy-domains (E-domain)** and domain spatial units (**DSU**);
- These elementary particles can further clump together to form *larger* particles/matter that possess additional pairs of lower order E-domains MWEPs.

Source of non-zero singularity gravity potential

What is gravity?

- As the sound pressure is a local pressure deviation from the ambient, the gravitational potential is the **local tension pressure** between the MWEP's radial **angular isotropic SSGT** and ambient isotropic E-space tension;
- The MWEP transformations produce angular isotropic residual radial spherical surface gradient tension (SSGT), aka E-space expansive transformation residual tension (EXTRT) (orange double arrow, T-R figure and figure (b)), such that $[(8\pi r/4\pi r^2) \times [1]_{\ell^2}]_{\ell^2/S^2}^{SSGT} [1]_{\ell^2/S^2}^{IELT} = [2]_{\ell^3/S^2}/[r]_{\ell}$ produced the gravitational potential with a normalized gravitational coupling constant $[2]_{\ell^3/S^2}$. E.g., the macroscopic Dc0-domain coupling constant is $[2]_{\ell^3/S^2} = [2R_0]_{m^3/S^2}$. Note that the ℓ demotes a natural length unit such that the isotropic E-space liner tension (IELT) and has unit value $[1]_{\ell^2/S^2}^{IELT}$.

Why gravitational potentials have non-zero-singularities?

- Because there is no infinite energy in nature, the energy-domains (**E-domain**), where gravitational potentials operate, have non-zero domain spatial units (**DSU**) such that gravitational potentials must have non-zero-singularities;
- By definition of the natural length unit ℓ , the isotropic E-space contains linear energy (**IELE**) $[1^2]_{\ell^2/S^4}^{IELE}$ (T-R figure); such that available IELE cannot support the MWEP transformation in the $r < [2]_{\ell}$ region because the transformation in this region would require higher than the available IELE, $[2]_{\ell^3/S^2}/[r]_{\ell} > [1]_{\ell^2/S^2}^{IELE}$ (blue circle T-R figure, figure (b)). Hence, gravitational potentials have non-zero-singularities $[2]_{\ell}$.

Multiple pairs of energy domain (E-domain)

There are multiple pairs of E-domains.

- Multiple E-domain pairs:** Because of conservation of energy law and disturbing energy can composed of multiple (Fourier) frequencies (as square wave is composed of multiple Fourier frequencies, B-R figure), the MWEP transformation can produce multiple pairs of complementary, **expansive** and **contractive**, gravitational potentials (T-R figure); each pair have their own energy domain (**E-domain**) spatial units ((**DSU**, ℓ):

 $[1]_{Dx\#} = [(32\pi)^{\#}c/2]_m$ for expansive **xE-domains** and

 $[1]_{Dc\#} = [R_0/(32\pi)^{\#}]_m$ for contractive **cE-domains**;
- Paired E-domains have complementary couplings $[2]_{\rho^3/s^2}$ but shares the speed limit $[2]_{Dx\#/s}$ that can be faster than light for high order E-domains; note that an astronomical gravity speed $[4]_{Dx5/s} = [2(32\pi)^5c]_{m/s}$ has been observed*;
- Newtonian gravity model only partially describes the macroscopic *contractive* gravitational potential Dc0-domain MWEP (**Dc0-MWEP**) that has a $[2]_{Dc0} = [2R_0]_m$ and a gravitational coupling constant $[2]_{Dc0^3/s^2} = [2R_0]_m^3/s^2$, which equals 99.43% of the 2014 CODATA-recommended gravitational constant value;
- Apart form Newtonian gravity, aka the macroscopic contractive **Dc0-MWEP**, traditional physics is unaware of the rest of gravitational potential; although the gravitational interaction effects of which have been observed; e.g., Pioneer spacecrafts sunward acceleration anomalies and strong coupling.

Inter/intra domain MWEPs

Inter/intra-domain MWEPs *can* have magnitude discontinuity at singularity.

- A MWEP is comprised of a particle like core (**E-fermion**) and an external field (**E-boson**) such that they possess **particle-wave duality**;
- Unlike the Newtonian gravitational potential that has **zero-singularity**, MWEPs have **non-zero singularities** at $[2]_{DSU}$, aka the E-fermion radius;
- Although a stand alone MWEP does not have **discontinuity** at singularity $[2]_{DSU}$ (red curves in right figures), the target-MWEP measured from a different order E-domain (**interdomain**, top figure) or harmonic E-domain (**intradomain**, bottom figure) has a **discontinuity-singularity** (vertical purple dot-dashed lines); this is because the inter/intra-domain transform coupling (**IDTC**, $T_c = \ell_t/\ell_f$ with the ℓ_t and ℓ_f as the target and reference E-domain DSU) affects the target-MWEP measurement;
- Note that real-world objects can have complex structures and various innate energy resolutions; a generic MWEP function is

$$P_M(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{\alpha^b}{r} \right]_{\ell^2} \frac{1}{s^2}, & \mathbf{r} \geq [R^m]_{\ell} \\ [\alpha^m]_{\ell^2} \frac{1}{s^2}, & \mathbf{r} < [R^m]_{\ell} \end{cases}$$

E-space Interdomain interaction potential (EIDIP)

The gravitational interaction energy imbalance produce another potential EIDIP, a single parameter T_c nonlinear function of distance.

- Although generic MWEF functions can be complex, this paper only deals with the simplest two-body interaction system that employs with a single parameter T_c target-centric MWEFs;
- The gravitational interaction energy imbalance between [R] and [L] regions (left figure, $[R] \neq [L]$) produces a potential, named E-space inter-domain (intra-domain) interaction potential (**EIDIP**);
- Short-range EIDIP effects are object asymmetrical because of target-centric $P_E^t = ([R] + [C]) - [L]$ differs from the reference-centric $P_E^f = [R] - ([C] + [L])$;
- However, long-range EIDIP effects are object-symmetrical approximately because of long-range $[R] \approx [C]$ for $r \rightarrow \infty$;
- EIDIPs are asymptotic are $P_E^+ \propto r$, and the long-range EIDIPs are ruly: $P_E^\infty \propto r^{-1}$; between which the EIDIP effects in the transition region are turbulent;
- Because MWEFs are **at-point** (divergence of a point) spherical potentials, the interaction between them is also an at-point operation such that the dual-sphere volume integral element is reduced to $dV = drd\theta d\varphi$ because the volume element $r^2 \sin \theta$ is neutralized by the at-point region element limit $1/|r^2 \sin \theta|$.

$$P_M^t(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{\ell^2}{s^2}}, r \geq [2T_c]_\ell \\ \left[1 \right]_{\frac{\ell^2}{s^2}}, r < [2T_c]_\ell \end{cases}$$

$$P_M^f(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{\ell^2}{s^2}}, r \geq [2]_\ell \\ \left[1 \right]_{\frac{\ell^2}{s^2}}, r < [2]_\ell \end{cases}$$

$$P_E(r_o; [T_c]) = 2\pi \iint \{P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t; [T_c]) \times \cos \theta\} d\theta dr_t$$

Short-range EIDIP are object-asymmetrical

Short-range EIDIP are turbulent and object-asymmetrical, whereas long-range EIDIP are ruly and object-symmetric approximately.

- Near-origin EIDIPs are asymptotic $P_E^+ \propto \mathbf{r}$, whereas the long-range EIDIPs are inversed distance functions: $P_E^\infty \propto \mathbf{r}^{-1}$;
- Short-range EIDIP are object asymmetrical because of $[R] \neq [L]$; i.e., the **target-centric** $P_E^t = ([R] + [C]) - [L]$ (R-T figure) differs from the **reference-centric** $P_E^f = [R] - ([C] + [L])$ (R-B figure); however, the long-range EIDIP are **approximately object-symmetrical** because of long-range $[R] \approx [L]$;
- The imbalance between the $[R]$ and $[L]$ regions produces a **system-differential-EIDIP** $P_{E[D]}$ (B-L figure); whereas the inter-object region $[C]$ produces a **system-core-EIDIP** $P_{E[C]}$ (B-M figure).

Dynamic EIDIP effects

The gravitational interactions between two dynamic body produce dynamic EIDIP effects which inherit all the EIDIP's strange behaviors.

- The dynamic gravitational interactions produce dynamic **EIDIP effects**; most of which are composed of rotational and irrotational components; e.g., **composite EIDIP** $rP'_r = P_d r^2 + P_r$ is composed of an irrotational **gradient-EIDIP** $P_d \equiv d(P_E)/dr$ (R-T figure) and a rotational **angular-EIDIP** $P_r \equiv rP_E$ (R-B figure);
- The dynamic gravitational interactions produce dynamic systemic EIDIP effects; e.g., **composite system-core-EIDIP** $rP'_{r[C]}$ (B-M figure), and **composite system-differential-EIDIP** $rP'_{r[D]}$ (B-L figure).

EIDIP effects can be partition into four quadrants

Inherited from EIDIP, short-range EIDIP effects are turbulent and object-asymmetric, whereas long-range EIDIP effects are ruly and object-symmetric ([1].III.A.1-2).

- Near-origin EIDIPs are asymptotic $P_E^+ \propto \mathbf{r}$, whereas the long-range EIDIPs are ruly: $P_E^\infty \propto 1/\mathbf{r}$ such that the EIDIP effects in the transition region are turbulent; the ruly near-origin and turbulent transition regions together referred as the **near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (NSTEE)** region (figure right);
- All NSTEEs **change directions** and some can even **change signs**, e.g., blue rP_r' and green r^2P_d' curves, R-figure); however, the long-range EIDIP effects are ruly; e.g., both the long-range green and red curves settle to constant;
- Along with the **contractive** cE- and **expansive** xE-domains, the EIDIP effects induced forces/phenomena can be divided into 4 quadrants: a distance-dependent **turbulent-ruly axis** and **contractive-expansive axis** ([1].X.C.2);
- The 4 types EIDIP effects induced phenomena are described by **disparate conventional models** with the aid of formfactors and **hypotheses**.

EIDIP effects induced phenomena examples	Short-range turbulent (NSTEE) object-asymmetrical	Long-rang ruly (conformal) object-symmetrical approximately
Contractive cE-domains Human scale to subatomic and beyond	Strong, weak, and residual strong forces; SR, Nuclear binding energy, covalent forces; hadron jets; subatomic dark matter; “new” 5 th fundamental force;	Electromagnetic forces; measured “virtual photon” mass; wide range of deviation between Newtonian gravity coupling constant measurements;
Expansive xE-domains Interplanetary to galactic and beyond	Beyond Newtonian limit relativistic phenomena and anomalies; GR, astrophysical jets; gravity waves; gravitoelectromagnetism	Beyond Newtonian limit relativistic phenomena and anomalies; dark matter; precession of Mercury; “new” <u>field theory</u> : $A \approx -\alpha/r$;

EIDIP effects induced Strong and EM interactions

Short-range turbulent EIDIP effects produced effective strong and residual strong couplings; whereas long-range ruly EIDIP effects produced effective electrostatic and magnetic couplings.

- The EIDIP effect $rP_r' = P_d r^2 + P_r$ (blue curve, T-R figure) comprises an irrotational coupling $P_d r^2$ (green curve, T-R figure) and a rotational coupling P_r (red curve, T-R figure; blue curve, B-R figure) ([1].VIII.E);
- In disparate conventional models, the short-range near singularity turbulent EIDIP effect (NSTEE) region $P_d r^2$ becomes the effective residual strong coupling (ERC) and the long-range ruly (conformal) region of which becomes the effective electrostatic coupling (EEC); whereas the NSTEE region P_r becomes the effective strong coupling (ESC, B-R figure) and the conformal region of which becomes the effective magnetic coupling (EMC);
- The P_r curve (red curve, T-R figure) depicts strong force's strange behaviors: asymptotic toward origin and color confinement (non-decaying) in long-range;
- The combinations of the rotational P_r -ESC (red curve, T-R figure) and the irrotational $P_d r^2$ -ERC (green curve) produce the $rP_r' \propto r^{-1}$ (blue curve, T-R figure) which has strong expulsive (positive) in the NSTEE region yet reduced to zero in short distance; which can explain the conundrum why strong interaction is non-decaying in long-range, and yet it has short interaction range; by which the conundrum ([1].VIII.E.5);
- Conventional models employ the virtual particles creation and annihilation to explain the conundrum; which can also be explain the short-range strong expulsive rP_r' .

Weak interaction is causal with EIDIP effects

EIDIP effects can unify the EM and weak interaction without the contradiction of electroweak unification.

- The weak interaction is responsible for the radioactive decay of atoms that it transforms a **neutron** into a **proton**, an **electron**, and an **electron antineutrino**. However, unifying the EM force and the weak force into an electroweak force in SM requires the force-carrying boson to be massless; which contradicts the SM's massive W boson assertion and requires the Higgs mechanism, the **massive-massless boson contradiction** of the conventional electroweak unification methods ([1].X.D.14);
- The NBE-EEPT has revealed that the nuclear binding energies (NBE), with which radioactive beta decays have **causal connections**, are produced by internucleon EIDIPs (T-R figure) ([1].V.A);
- The NCD-EEPT (M-R figure) and PCD-EEPT (B-R figure) have revealed their **causal** relationship with the EIDIP effects couplings; hence, the weak interaction phenomena between the proton and neutron transformation are the byproducts of EIDIP effects couplings transformations that are free of the massive-massless bosons contradiction; i.e., the weak interaction is an omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (**OEIA**).

Long-range EIDIP effects can overpower gravity

Some long-range EIDIP effects are non-decaying that they are observable and can even overpower gravity in some astronomical range.

- The strengths of xE-domain EIDIP effects are neglectable in macro scale; however, they are observable at interplanetary distance, and can even surpass and dominant gravity at some galactic distance;
- Because gravity strength decreases with inverse distance square whereas some of the expansive astronomical EIDIP effects are non-decaying, e.g., $P_r^\infty \propto r^0$; these astronomical non-decaying EIDIP effects are observable in some interplanetary distance (e.g., the observed Pioneer spacecraft anomalies), and they can even surpass Newton gravity at some astronomical distance and become dominant (e.g., the P_r^∞ underlying the Pioneer spacecrafts anomalies, T-R figure, [1].VII.C.2);
- Because the Keplerian predictions are unaware of these permeating astronomic EIDIP effects, they would require much higher mass than observable, aka **dark matter**, to explain the unaware and dominant EIDIP effects, a type of omitting EIDIP effect induced artifacts (OEIA) ([1].IX.B and more examples in [1].X.D); e.g., the dark matter required to explain the galaxy rotation curves anomalies; in MWRC anomaly cases, the EIDIP effects can overpower the gravity by 2+ orders magnitude (B-R figure , dotted-dash box, blue: EIDIP effects, green: gravity).

Null hypothesis test node (NHTN) method

Null hypothesis testing node (NHTD) method can give a quantitative estimate to accept or reject that the EIDIP framework.

- In physics, one can argue that no one can prove anything because unknown future discoveries, i.e., even all known physical phenomena are not a complete sampling pool;
- However, we can use a null hypothesis testing node (NHTD) method to compute how likely a hypothesis is true;
- Null hypothesis testing nodes (NHTD) are the fitness of the EEPT; e.g., the purple EIDIP curve in the top figures (green dots: the 2438 nuclei listed in the AME2012 table with experimental nuclear binding energy; black dots: elements in the Periodic table) and the blue gradient-EIDIP curve in the bottom figure; which traces the black mean curve of the [empirical IACF curve \(tip-2\)*](#);
- The NHTDs also include those uncanny components of the EEPT; e.g., the distance to mass number scalar $\mathbf{A} = [r]_m/[R_u]_m$ with $R_u = [1/c^2]_m$ which revealed the quantized lower bound inter-particle distance (LBID) unit, and the the P_E based semi-empirical formula EPNBE-SEF have a lower **0.094** standard deviation than the **0.415** standard deviation produced by the liquid-drop Bethe-Weizsäcker NBE-SEF.

EIDIP framework has 7+ Sigma statistical proof

Nulling EIDIP's existence has 7+ sigma statistical significance.

- Because of unknown future discoveries, all known physical phenomena cannot be treated as a complete sampling space to **prove** a hypothesis or theory. E.g., although the existence of the EIDIP effects functions is objective, the physical phenomena described by them can be coincidental; hence, the 10+ EEPTs cannot **prove** the underlying EIDIP's existence. However, the evidence revealed in the 10+ EEPTs can yield a *qualitative* confirmation. E.g., the logical probability of the EIDIP's existence can be calculated by a null hypothesis testing node (**NHTD**) method;
- The EIDIP framework includes a quantitative simple calculus EIDIP equation (equation 19) and a qualitative EIDIP framework ([1].II, IV, and IX) accompany with 10+ computational (MATLAB, [2]) phenomenological test cases (verifiability, fairness) against real-world measurements ([1].V-VIII) that “prove” the unification of forces with 7+ sigma statistical significance level ([1].X.B) (verifiability). The objectivity of these MATLAB simulations is inarguable (verifiability, fairness). The gravitational interaction potential framework comes with a long list of falsifiable salient predictions (predictability, falsifiability).

Primary null hypotheses test Node (P-NHTD):

- The 10+ EEPTs themselves are primary NHTDs because those single shaping-parameter nonlinear EIDIP effects can phenomenological fit to those complex empirical figures or datasets are uncanny;
- Those NSTEE region EEPTs with integer DSU distance scalars are primary NHTDs because that they can scale the single shaping-parameter NSTEE curves to fit those complex physical phenomena are uncanny;
- The 10+ EEPTs' inter-domain coupling T_c are primary NHTDs because that they share only two values, $(32\pi)^{1/4}$ and 32π are uncanny;
- There are **54 P-NHTD**, each assigned with a conservative 0.5 probability for being coincidental, which yields a 7+ Sigma significance with **15 P-NHTDs** to spare.

Free of these statistical pitfalls: e.g.,

- **Selective-sampling (cherry picking) pitfall:** The 10+ EEPTs cover subatomic-to-interstellar anomalous-or-not physical phenomena; i.e., they are not selective samples;
- **Compound-statistic pitfall:** these P-NHTDs are connected by the EIDIP; i.e., they are not compound samples;
- **Overfitting pitfall:** the EIDIP framework is based on a simple calculus EIDIP equation (equation 19) and a intuitive qualitative EIDIP framework ([1].II, IV, and IX).

Gravity is the only fundamental forces

Gravitational interaction potential produced other fundamental-or-not forces: e.g.,

- The turbulent near singularity Dc2.5-EIDIP effects produced the subatomic strong force (SF), neutron-neutron potential (NNP), effective strong coupling (ESC), effective residual strong coupling (ERC); of which the long-range ruly produced the effective electrostatic coupling (EEC), effective magnetic coupling (EMC) [1].VIII.E);
- The turbulent near singularity Dc2-EIDIP produced the internucleon nuclear binding energy (NBE) ([1].V.A);
- The turbulent near singularity Dc0-angular-EIDIP produced Bohr radius;
- The weak interaction phenomena between the proton and neutron transformation can be described by EIDIP effects couplings transformations, a type of omitting EIDIP effect induced artifacts (OEIAs);

- The turbulent near singularity Dc0-gradient-EIDIP effects produced the interatomic covalent force (IACF) ([1].VI.A) and intermolecular Casimir forces (IMCF);
- The turbulent near singularity Dx2-angular-EIDIP produced the interplanetary Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 sunward acceleration anomalies (PSAA) ([1].VII.C);
- The turbulent near singularity Dx5-EIDIP effects produced the intergalactic galaxies rotation curve anomalies: ([1].VIII.F-G.); e.g., Milky Way rotation curve (MWRC) anomaly;
- The turbulent near singularity xE-EIDIP effects can produced the astrophysical jets near black holes;
- Most of dark matters are OEIAs ([1].X.D.6);
- cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects are symmetrical such that the astronomical Gravitoelectromagnetism and relativistic adjustments (GR) are likely xE-domain OEIAs.

7+ Sigma statistical proof implications

EIDIP framework with 7+ Sigma statistical proof is disruptive mainly because current physics is unaware of the EIDIP underlying various phenomena/anomalies:

- The 10+ EEPs have revealed, with 7+ Sigma “proof”, that EIDIP effects permeate everywhere and can describe and unify a wide range of physical phenomena without form factors;
- Because current physics is unaware of the permeating EIDIP, it is safe to say that **omitting EIDIP effect induced artifacts (OEIA)** are wide spread in current physical models and data and have led to **disparate conventional models**;
- **All matters and energy entities possess MWEP-like energy structures regardless of their size:** e.g., the photon antibunching and gravitational lensing;
- Paired E-domains implicate that there could be **yet-to-be-identified Dc5-domain elementary particles** or elementary particles’ sizes are **5 orders magnitude off**;
- High-order gravities and EIDIP effects are **faster than light**; e.g., the speed of gravity wave;
- Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects and **isomorphic magnitude formula**; which are good for knowledge pollinating across physics fields.

Omitting EIDIP effect induced artifacts (OEIA) appear in various types: e.g.,

- **Strong interaction:** subatomic NSTEE region angular-EIDIP P_r induced phenomena;
- **Electromagnetic forces:** long-range ruly angular- and gradient EIDIP effects induced forces;
- **Weak interaction:** the weak interaction during the proton to neutron transformation is part of the EIDIP effects $d(P_E)/dr \leftrightarrow P_E/r$ transformation;
- **Relativistic adjustments:** e.g., gravitational frame dragging and red shifts;
- **Formfactors:** e.g., neutron charge distribution and astrophysical jets formfactors;
- **Anomalies:** e.g., Pioneer spacecrafts and galaxy rotation curves anomalies; near earth flyby anomalies;
- **Mysteries:** e.g., neutron electric dipole moment problem and Proton spin crisis;
- **Dark elements:** e.g. dark matter, dark energy;
- **Hypothetic Yukawa potentials:** the astronomic of which are **electromagnetic (Gravitoelectromagnetism)** whereas the subatomic of which are **gravitational**;
- **Duality:** the MWEP is composed of a particle-like E-fermion core and a wave-like E-boson field that it exhibits the wave-particle duality.

EIDIP framework vs. other GUTs

Natural law is unique; although there are many competing partial models, only one can be true (or the truest):

- Theoretical frameworks can be judged through these major scientific precepts and the EIDIP framework possesses: **Verifiability, predictability, falsifiability, fairness (scope, utility, expediency), simplicity, consistency, accuracy, progressiveness;**
- Conventional models are unaware of the expansive type gravity and the EIDIP effects; hence, those GUT based on conventional models **cannot** complete describe them;
- Those GUTs assume that gravity and other fundamental have **peer-to-peer** relationship (i.e., merging in high energy) would fail because they have **parent-to-children** relationships;
- Accuracy requires mathematical descriptions; those GUTs lacking such **cannot** be accurate (**pseudo science**).

	EIDIP framework	Other GUTs
Verifiability	Publicly verifiable data, MATLAB program, EIDIP equations and EIDIP framework description;	some can not be verified; e.g., string theory;
Predictability	Has a long list of falsifiable predictions and implications;	Limited? Cannot cover the sign direction or changing NSTEEs even with high # of variables;
Falsifiability	Long list predictions inherited from EIDIP's strange ruly-turbulent behaviors;	Limited? Cannot cover the sign direction or changing NSTEEs even with high # of variables;
Fairness	Can describe subatomic to galactic range phenomena and anomalies;	Limited? Cannot cover the sign direction or changing NSTEEs even with high # of variables;
Simplicity	Intuitive; plain calculus math and classical mechanics; can unify gravity with other forces; can unify disparate conventional models;;	Nonintuitive; require complicated math, formfactors, hypothetic Yukawa potential, time/length dilatation, space-time, or 10+ dimensions;
Accuracy	Has quantitative plain calculus EIDIP effect equations to produce accurate results;	Based on incomplete models (e.g., GR, SM) or lacking mathematical descriptions

Null hypothesis test node (NHTN) method

Null hypothesis testing node (NHTD) method can give a quantitative estimate to accept or reject that the EIDIP framework.

- In physics, one can argue that no one can prove anything because unknown future discoveries, i.e., even all known physical phenomena are not a complete sampling pool;
- However, we can use a null hypothesis testing node (NHTD) method to compute how likely the null hypothesis “the underlying EIDIP dose not exist” is true;
- Null hypothesis testing nodes (NHTD) are the fitness of the EEPTs and those uncanny components of which;
- E.g., the purple EIDIP curve traces upper bound nuclear binding energy of known nuclei in the top figures (green dots: the 2438 nuclei listed in the AME2012 table with experimental nuclear binding energy; black dots: elements in the Periodic table) and the blue gradient-EIDIP curve traces the black mean curve of the [empirical IACF curve \(tip-2\)*](#) (B-R figure);
- E.g., the distance to mass number scalar $A = [r]_m/[R_u]_m$ with $R_u = [1/c^2]_m$ which revealed the quantized lower bound inter-particle distance (LBID) unit, and the the P_E based semi-empirical formula EPNBE-SEF have a lower **0.094** standard deviation than the **0.415** standard deviation produced by the [liquid-drop Bethe-Weizsäcker NBE-SEF](#);
- However, one can still argue that these uncanny NHTDs can still be coincidental; to account for that, each NHTD is assigned with a conservative 0.5 probability for the null hypothesis “the underlying EIDIP dose not exist”, i.e., these uncanny NHTNs are just coincidental; the 0.5 probability is conservative because that statistically, the probability of a single shaping-parameter nonlinear EIDIP or derived function can describe a nonlinear physical phenomenon by chance is low;
- With a number of n NHTDs, the possibility of all these NHTDs are coincidental is 0.5^n .

Section 3

Nulling EIDIP effects has 7+ Sigma significance

Although one cannot prove but disapprove a physics hypothesis or theory, a null hypothesis testing node (NHTD) method can give a quantitative estimate to accept or reject the null hypothesis:

- Because of unknown future discoveries, all known physical phenomena cannot be treated as a complete sampling space to prove a hypothesis or theory; e.g., although the EIDIP effects functions is objective, it is fair to say that the physical phenomena described by EIDIP effects can be just coincidental;
- However, it is also fair to say that the more physical phenomena the EIDIP effects can describe, the lower probability that these phenomenological fits are just coincidental;
- In science, 5 Sigma significance, corresponding to about 1 in $1.7e6$ that the result is a random fluke, is generally the accepted threshold for legitimate discoveries. However, it is also reasonable to require that extraordinary claims that affect fundamental physics and could overhaul many physics fields to have extraordinary evidences beyond the 5 Sigma statistical proof.

Nulling the EIDIP effects already has a 7+ Sigma significance with these 54 primary P-NHTDs with 15 P-NHTDs to spare:

- Statistically, the probability of a single shaping-parameter (T_c) nonlinear EIDIP effect functions can by chance describe an unrelated nonlinear physical phenomenon is very low; i.e., way lower than 0.5 probability;
- With each uncanny NHTD assigned with a conservative 0.5 probability to be “just coincidental”, it would require at least **39 NHTDs** to achieve the **7 Sigma significance**: 1 in $3.9e11$ and $2^{39} \cong 5.5e11$;
- Those **54 P-NHTDs** (36 presented in individual slides plus 18 T_c -related presented in the summary slide) yield a qualitative confirmation that nulling the EIDIP effects has a **7+ Sigma significance** with **15 P-NHTDs to spare**;
- If we include those uncanny **27 S-NHTDs** and additional **15 Y-NHTDs**, nulling the EIDIP effects would have a 7+ Sigma significance with total of **57 NHTDs to spare**;
- In short, these NHTDs have provided a **statistical proof** that **the EIDIP effects** underlying a wide range of phenomena **do exist**.

7+ Sigma significance avoids statistical pitfalls

Statistical pitfalls can produce artificial results:* e.g.,

- **Selective-sampling (cherry picking) pitfall:** intentionally selecting data points to help support a particular hypothesis; e.g., using Asian lottery winners as sampling pool to conclude winning is race related;
- **Compound-statistic (Data Dredging, multiplicity) pitfall:** intentionally selecting *unrelated* data points or attributes to help support a particular hypothesis;
- **Overfitting pitfall:** creating an extremely complex and overly tailored model to fit the dataset;
- **Survivorship Bias (incomplete samples) pitfall:** drawing conclusions from incomplete data; which also is the reason that **one cannot prove anything in physics** (because of unknown future discoveries, there is **no** complete sample set in physics). However, NHTD methods can give a quantitative estimate to accept or reject hypothesis.

The 7+ Sigma significance is free of these statistical pitfalls:

- **Selective-sampling (cherry picking) pitfall:** The 10+ EEPTs' physical phenomena cover subatomic-to-interstellar anomalous-or-not physical phenomena such that they are not selective samples;
- **Compound-statistic (Data Dredging, multiplicity) pitfall:** Although the 10+ EEPTs' physical phenomena are conventionally described by disparate models or as anomalies, they are connected by the EIDIP; i.e., these EEPTs are not compound samples and those NHTDs are not *unrelated* data points;
- **Overfitting pitfall:** The EIDIP framework is started with a plain one parameter calculus EIDIP equation ([1].equ.19) and an intuitive qualitative model ([1].II, IV, and IX); i.e., the EIDIP framework is not an complex or overfit model;
- **Survivorship Bias (incomplete samples) pitfall:** There is no complete samples in physics; however, that the 10+ EEPTs covers a wide range phenomena does minimize the survivorship bias.

Importance of 7+ Sigma significance

Extraordinary claims requires extraordinary evidences beyond the 5 Sigma statistical proof:

- In science, 5 Sigma significance, corresponding to about a one-in-a-million that the result is a random fluke, is generally the accepted threshold for legitimate discoveries. However, it is also reasonable to require that extraordinary claims that affect fundamental physics and could overhaul many physics fields to have extraordinary evidences beyond the 5 Sigma statistical proof;
- Without the 7+ Sigma statistical proof, the EIDIP framework's prowess (simplicity, utility, scope and progressiveness) and disruptive implications would just appear as red herrings; however, with acceptance of the **7+ Sigma statistical proof**, they become **natural** and **logical**;
- The translation from the EIDIP effects to conventional models are mostly yet to be developed such that the **7+ Sigma statistical proof** is **paramount** and **pivotal** for physicists to embrace the change.

EIDIP framework affect fundamental physics and will overhaul many physics fields:

- EIDIP effects induced phenomena can be partitioned into **four quadrants** (table below); because current physics are unaware of the EIDIP connections, current models are **incomplete** and **partial**; e.g., the currently defined gravity and Coulombic couplings are not truly constants;
- The 7+ Sigma significance **statistical proof** of "EIDIP effects do exist" will make unifying these disparate conventional models **necessary** and **logical** such that it will overhaul many physics fields.

EIDIP effects	Short-range turbulent object-asymmetrical	Long-range ruly object-symmetrical
Contractive cE-domains	Partially observed and modeled	Mostly observed and modeled
Expansive xE-domains	Observed but not or partially modeled	Observed but not or partially modeled

EIDIP framework's scientific method

Natural law is unique; although there are many competing partial models, only one can be the truest. Theoretical frameworks can be judged through these major scientific precepts which the EIDIP framework possesses:

- **Verifiability:** all EEPTs are based on verified publicly available data and published MATLAB program [2];
- **Predictability:** EIDIP framework has a long list of falsifiable predictions and implications ([1].X.C-D);
- **Falsifiability:** the EIDIP effects are fundamentally falsifiable because they have the multi-singularities signatures inherited from the quantized-singularity of the underlying MWEPs (e.g., [1].X.C.3);
- **Fairness, Scope, Utility:** EIDIP effects can describe a wide range of, from subatomic to intergalactic, physical phenomena that are currently described by segmented conventional models; EIDIP effects can unify gravity with other fundamental-or-not and anomalous forces;
- **Simplicity:** EIDIP framework is based on a **plain calculus EIDIP equation:** $P_E(r_o; [T_c]) = 2\pi \iint \{P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t; [T_c]) \times \cos \theta\} d\theta dr_t;$

- **Consistency:** the EIDIP effects can consistently describe the behaviors of a wide range of physical phenomena currently described by **disparate conventional models** or as **anomalies**;
- **Accuracy:** EIDIP framework does not require conventional formfactors; the EIDIP based semi-empirical formula (**SEF**) for nuclear binding energy (NBE) and nuclear charge radii (**NCR**) are comparable to, if not more accurate than, the conventional NBE and NCR SEF formula ([1].V.A.3); the angular-EIDIP can trace both the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11's steep ascending and slow descending anomalous sunward acceleration;
- **Progressiveness:** The non-perturbative EIDIP framework can gain insights from the 10+ three-variable EEPTs that perturbative or high variable count models cannot; the gained insights have provided coherent first-order rationales for additional non-classical physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit ([1].X.D).

Under the principle of Occam's razor, among competing hypotheses that predict equally well, the simplest one with the fewest assumptions and variables should be selected

Section 3

Fairness, Scope, Utility, and Progressiveness

EIDIP framework can describe a wide range of phenomena (fairness, scope, utility) ([1].X.B): e.g.,

- Asymptotic and conformal behaviors of strong interaction without particle form factors;
- Subatomic neutron and proton charge distributions, which are EIDIP effects couplings distributions, without charge density form factors;
- The upper bound of the internucleon nuclear binding energy for almost all known nuclei without particle form factors;
- Distance-dependent repulsive-attractive behaviors of the subatomic nuclear force and interatomic covalent force without particle form factors;
- The relationship between these effective couplings: residual-strong, strong, electrostatic, and magnetic without particle and charge density form factors;
- Interatomic Bohr radius;
- The large deviation between the gravitational constant measurements;
- Both the steep ascending and the slow descending data of the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft anomalies;
- Astronomical MW rotation curve anomalies without dark matter form factors.

EIDIP framework's nonperturbative single parameter nonlinear EIDIP effects functions have rigid shapes such that they can gain insights those high number variables models can not (Progressiveness) ([1].XI.2):

- With the gained insights, the EIDIP framework can also provide coherent first-order rationales for additional physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit;
- E.g., particle-wave duality, proton spin crisis, neutron electric dipole moment problem, photon antibunching, dark matter, dark energy, accelerating expansion of the universe, galaxy formation, astrophysical and hadron jets, gravitational lensing and frame-dragging, gravitational time dilation measurement, quantum decoherence, quantum entanglement, astronomical gravitoelectromagnetism, black hole structure, gravity wave, and near-Earth flyby anomaly.

Falsifiable and verifiable predictions

The EIDIP framework's falsifiable and verifiable predictions: e.g.,

- Gradient-EIDIP produced forces (e.g., residual-strong and covalent forces) do not rise infinitely near origin and have additional singularities in the repulsive regions;
- **Newtonian gravity model is incomplete:** macroscopic gravity potentials have non-zero singularity and have entangled complementary expansive gravity potentials;
- **GR is incomplete:** Monochromatic Relativistic adjustments $(v/c)^2$ cannot cover the sign-changing near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects ([1].X.D.17);
- The projectile swing by radius R_{SF}^{max} and the internucleon radius R_{NNP}^{max} are the major components of the measured nuclear charge radii (NCR) especially for light nuclei; and protons have rigid core (which has been affirmed*1);
- Those beyond Newtonian limit phenomena observed, most of them are omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (OEIAs); e.g., dark matter ([1].IX.B);
- Disparate conventional models are one type of OEIAs;
- The centripetal force in the center of black holes is close to zero because gravity has non-zero singularity, and EIDIP effects are asymptotic or expulsive near origin ([1].X.D.20).

The EIDIP framework's falsifiable and verifiable implications: e.g.,

- E-domains come in entangled complementary pair such that discovery of one also indicate the existence of other; e.g., the MWRC EEPTs revealed that the Dx5-EIDIP exist such that there are Dc5-elementary particles; either there are yet-to-be-identified, or quarks are Dc5-elementary particles such that SF and NNP are actually Dc5, not Dc2.5 phenomena ([1].X.C.4);
- High-order gravities and EIDIP effects are faster than light of which some have observed*2 ([1].II.D.4);
- Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects and Isomorphic EIDIP effects magnitude formula; hence, the knowledge gained from one is applicable to the other ([1].IX.E);
- EIDIP effects' multiple local minimums can induce Object- and systemic-EIDIPs' preferred distances (OSPD) OSPD-misalignment oscillations and tunneling effects; the former could be the origin of matters' innate temperature; whereas the latter could induce the observed cold-to-hot heat transfer "time reversal" quantum phenomena ([1].IV.D).

Section 3

*1:<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/365/6457/1007>; *2 Carlip, S.(1999);

“EIDIP does exist” has profound implications

The EIDIP effects do exist everywhere, some are strong enough to be observed, and some are only noticeable in astronomical distance.

- The EIDIP does exist may not mean much if the effects of which is neglectable. However, the PSAA and MWRC EEPs have revealed that the some astronomical EIDIP effects are non-decaying (e.g., $P_r^\infty \propto r^0$, blue line, B-L PSAA figure) such that they can cross over the gravity ($\propto r^{-2}$, green line, B-L figure) and can even overpower gravity by orders of magnitude (blue-dashed box, B-R figure);
- Coulombic constant tries to represent a settle-to-constant EIDIP effect coupling (not a true constant) such that the **virtual photon mass** measurements actually measures the **deviation** of the settle-to-constant EIDIP coupling (e.g., $r^2 P_d^\infty \propto r^0$) from the *defined* Coulombic constant.

Disruptive implications: e.g.,

- All matter and energy entities possess MWEP-like energy structures;
- The omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (OEIA) are wide spread and can appear in various forms: e.g., formfactors, dark matter, anomalies; ([1].IX.B)
- Neither the repulsive residual-strong and covalent forces nor the gravitational potentials rise to infinity;
- There are **yet-to-be-identified Dc5 elementary particles**;
- The **disparate conventional models** (e.g., GR, QM, and EM) partially describe different types and regions of EIDIP effects;
- The object-symmetrical short-range EIDIP effects could induced the observed **CP violations**;
- The long-range composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing effects ([1].VIII.E.5) could explain the **short strong interaction range**;
- EIDIP effects' multi local minimums induced effects can induce matters' **innate temperature** and **gravitational waves**; the tuning effect from which can the observed “cold-to-hot heat transfer” quantum phenomena.

All matter and energy entities possess MWEPs

The 10+ EEPTs have shown that EIDIP effects can describe the interactions of elementary and composite particles: quark, electron, nucleon, and atom to astronomical objects without massless force-carrying bosons: photon, gluon, and hypothetical graviton and astronomic bosons ([1].IX.D): e.g.,

- The subatomic angular EIDIP P_r between **quarks** can describe the strong interaction **without gluon**;
- The subatomic EIDIP-gradient P_d between **quarks** can describe the residual-strong force **without gluon**;
- The EIDIP between **nucleons** can describe the nuclear binding energy (NBE) **without gluon**;
- The subatomic turbulent EIDIP effects couplings between **quarks** can describe the ERC and ESC **without gluon** whereas the residual EIDIP effects couplings can describe the EMC and EEC between **particles without virtual photon**;
- Subatomic expulsive and attractive EIDIP effects couplings can describe neutron and proton charge distributions **without positive and negative charges**;
- The interatomic angular EIDIP P_r between **atom and electron** can describe the Bohr radius **without virtual photon**;
- The Dc0-domain MWEPs E-boson coupling $2R_0$ plus the long-range IACF coupling can fit the value of the Newtonian gravitational constant closely. The long-range IACF coupling's contribution can explain the wide deviation between the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements; i.e., the EIDIP framework can describe macroscopic gravitational interaction between **matters without the hypothetical graviton**;
- The EIDIP effects between **astronomical objects** can describe the gravitational anomalies and galaxy structures without dark matters and hypothetical astronomical range bosons and YuKawa potential;
- In short, these 10+ EEPTs have revealed that these objects: photon, quark, nucleon, electron, atoms, molecules, regular matter, and even astronomical objects possess the MWEP. Photons' particle-wave duality and antibunching behaviors also affirm that photons possess the MWEP. I.e., **all energy entities (matter, particles, photons, etc.) possess the MWEP regardless of their size.**

EIDIP effects are asymptotically safe

The EIDIP induced phenomena, e.g., residual-strong and covalent forces, do not rise to infinity, i.e., asymptotically safe ([1].X.C.3):

- The ruly EIDIP effect $P_E^+ \propto r$ near origin produced the angular EIDIP asymptotic segment $P_r^+ = rP_E^+ \propto r^2$ (green curve left of red dashed line, left figure) and EIDIP-gradient saturated segment $P_d^+ = d(P_E^+)/dr \propto r^0$ (blue line left of red dashed line);
- The strong force is well known to be asymptotic toward origin ($P_r^+ \propto r^2$) such that it also affirms the saturated segments of gradient-EIDIP effects induced phenomena ($P_d^+ \propto r^0$, blue curve, T-R figure): e.g., subatomic residual strong force, interatomic covalent force, and Intermolecular van der Waals force;
- EIDIP effects are asymptotically safe: either settle to constant ($\propto r^0$, e.g., gradient-EIDIP. blue curve, T-R figure) or propotional to $r^\#$ with $\#$ being positive (e.g., green curve, T-R figure; green and blue curves, B-R figure);
- With that both the MWEPs and EIDIP effects are asymptotically safe, and that Infinite energy does not exist in nature, the centripetal forces in the center of black holes should also be asymptotically safe.

Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects

Symmetrical cE- and xE-MWEPs produce Symmetrical cE- and xE-EIDIP effects that have Isomorphic EIDIP effects magnitude formula ([1].IV.E).

- E.g., the cE-domain NSTEE region angular-EIDIP P_r underlying the strong interaction (B-L figure) also exists in xE-domains such that it produces the PSAA anomaly (B-M figure);
- Astrophysical jets and hadron jets can be produced by the symmetrical cE- and xE-EIDIP effects respectively (B-R figure);
- EIDIP effects magnitude formula have shared terms; e.g., $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ (table right);
- The knowledge we learn from EIDIP effects induced phenomena can cross pollenate the others; e.g., **gravitoelectromagnetism**.

EEPT	E-dom	Magnitude formula
IACF	Dc0	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times M_{kg}^{IACF}]_N^{PGA}$ $M_{kg}^{IACF} = [1/4(32\pi)^3]_{kg}$
NGCD	Dc0	$[P_d^\infty \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times [1]_{kg}^{NGCD}]_N^{PGA}$
NNP	Dc2.5	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times (M_{kg}^{NNP} c^2)]_N^{PGA}$ $M_{kg}^{NNP} \rightarrow [1]_{eV/c^2}$
SF	Dc2.5	$[P_r \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times (2_{Dx25}^2)]_N^{APA}$
PSAA	Dc2	$[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_\odot \times (2_{Dc2}^2) \times 1_{Dx2}]_N^{APA}$
PG-MWRC	Dx5	$[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_{kg}^{EP} \times (2_{Dc2}^2) \times 4]_N$
EMC	Dc2.5	$[(P_r^\infty / r^2) \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{APA}$

Omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (OEIAs)

Omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (OEIA) are wide spread and can appear in various types ([1].IX.B):

- **Disparate models:** to describe the short-range turbulent and long-range ruly of the same EIDIP effects; e.g., the strong and weak interactions for subatomic turbulent EIDIP effects near singularities, whereas the EM models for long-range ruly EIDIP effects;
- **Form factors:** to describe the observed NSTEE phenomena; e.g., subatomic neutron charge distribution and astronomical astrophysical jet formfactors;
- **Relativistic adjustments:** e.g., gravitational frame dragging and red shifts;
- **Anomalies:** those beyond the Newtonian limits phenomena: e.g., Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft sunward acceleration anomalies, near earth flyby anomalies;
- **Mysteries/crisis/problems:** e.g., neutron electric dipole moment problem and Proton spin crisis;
- **Hypothetic potential:** the hypothetic astronomic electromagnetic but subatomic gravitational Yukawa potentials;
- **Dark mater:** some of the settle-to-constant EIDIP effects, can overpower the gravity at some astronomical distance by orders of magnitude;
- **Dark energy:** intergalactic expulsive composite EIDIP effects can produced the observed accelerating expansion of the universe;
- Precession of Mercury and bending of light;
- **Gravitoelectromagnetism;**
- Measured **virtual photon mass:** The measured virtual photon mass based on the Coulombic coupling constant, of which the coupling is settle-to-constant but not constant;
- **New particles or forces:** e.g., the new 5th fundamental force; the “new” field theory, $A \approx -\alpha/r'$ (PHYSICS ESSAYS 33, 4 (2020)).

OEIA type: Disparate conventional models

Current physics is unaware of the EIDIP effects such that they require disparate models with aid of formfactors or relativistic adjustments to describe each quadrant of EIDIP effects induced phenomena ([1].X.C.2).

- The 10+ EEPs have revealed that the EIDIP effects permeate space, from subatomic to galactic and beyond; and that the short-range turbulent (NSTEE) and long-range ruly EIDIP effects (B-R figure) are described by separated conventional models (B-L figure, [1].Fig.68);

- The strengths of xE-domain EIDIP effects are neglectable in macro scale; however, some are observable at interplanetary distance, and some can even surpass and **dominate** gravity at some galactic distance;
- Although most of the ruly EIDIP effects have been well described by classical physics models, some relatively low-intensity astronomical EIDIP effects induced physical phenomena are beyond the Newtonian limit such that they require relativistic adjustments, formfactors, or remain as anomalies.

OEIA type: Dark matters

Some long-range EIDIP effects are non-decaying that they are observable and can even overpower gravity in some astronomical range ([1].X.D.6).

- Astronomical dark matters:** The strengths of xE-domain EIDIP effects are neglectable in macro scale; however, they are observable at interplanetary distance, and can even surpass and dominant gravity at some galactic distance. This is because gravity strength decreases with inverse distance square whereas some of the expansive astronomical EIDIP effects are non-decaying (although energy leaky) e.g., $P_r^\infty \propto r^0$; these astronomical non-decaying EIDIP effects are can surpass Newton gravity at some astronomical distance and even become dominant by orders magnitude (e.g., by 2+ orders magnitude, dotted-dash box, T-R figure; green: gravity, blue: EIDIP effects; [1].VIII.G.4). Because the Keplerian predictions are unaware of these permeating astronomic EIDIP effects, they require much higher mass than observable, aka **dark matter**, to explain the EIDIP effects induced dark force;
- Ditto for the **subatomic dark matters:** EIDIP effects are turbulent near the singularity (e.g., NSTEE region, B-R figure); because not all the subatomic EIDIP effects induced forces have been observed and modeled (E.G., the 100+ particles), those newly observed dark forces would require **dark matter** to explain them.

OEIA type: Formfactors

Form factors are functions measured experimentally to encapsulate the properties of a certain interaction without including all the underlying physics; e.g., the quantum field and elementary particle form factors, charge density, and dark matter distribution ([1].X.D.12).

- The ESC, SF, NNP, and NBE EEPTs have revealed that EIDIP effects can describe these phenomena without the quantum field or particle form factors;
- The NCD and PCD EEPTs have revealed that the EIDIP couplings can describe these charge distributions without the electromagnetic or charge density form factors;
- The IACF and IMVF EEPTs have revealed that the EIDIP effect can describe these forces without atomic form factors;
- The PSAA and MWRC EEPTs have revealed that astronomical EIDIP effects can explain these **anomalies** without the dark matter distribution form factors;
- The astronomical expulsive EIDIP effects (B-R figure) can induced the astrophysical jets without **expulsive gravitoelectromagnetic formfactors**.

Yet-to-be-identified Dc5 elementary particles

Paired and entangled E-domains implications

([1].X.C.4):

- All energy entities can possess pairs of entangled MWEPs, between which the interactions also produced pairs of entangled EIDIP effects (table left); e.g., the Dc0-EIDIP effects that produce the IACF and Bohr radius have counter part Dx0-EIDIP effects that produce the near-earth flyby anomalies;
- The MWRC-EEPTs revealed that matters, including astronomical objects, possess Dx5-MWEPs from which their Dx5-EIDIP effects originate;
- The subatomic EEPTs (e.g., SF-EEPT) revealed that the elementary particles operate in the Dc2.5-domain; i.e., there are currently no known Dc5-domain elementary particles;
- If the hypothesis that matters possess paired MWEPs is true, matters should also possess yet-to-be-identified Dc5-domain elementary particles;
- Or the currently known elementary particles actually operate in the Dc5-domain instead of Dc2.5-domain such that their scale or the interaction range would be 5 orders of magnitude shorter than the current ones constructed from the conventional models (e.g., constant coupling Coulombic force).

E-domain	Physical phenomena
D_{c0}	Interatomic covalent force and Bohr radius;
D_{x0}	<i>Near-Earth-flyby anomalies;</i>
D_{c2}	Internucleon nuclear binding energy; <i>Interquark strong and residual-strong interactions ($D_{c2.5}$ is a harmonic of the D_{c2};</i>
D_{x2}	Pioneer sunward acceleration anomaly;
$D_{c2.5}$	Interquark strong and residual-strong interactions;
$D_{x2.5}$	<i>Astronomical gravitational anomalies;</i>
D_{c5}	<i>Yet-to-be-identified elementary particles; or SF and NNP are Dc5-domain phenomena, and quarks are Dc5-domain elementary particles;</i>
D_{x5}	Milky Way and galaxy rotation curve anomalies;

Why Newtonian gravity model is incomplete

Newtonian gravity model dose not cover these characteristics of gravitational potentials:

- **Non-zero-singularity:** There is NO infinite energy existing in nature, hence, gravitational potentials have non-zero-singularities;
- By definition of the natural length unit ℓ , the isotropic E-space contains linear energy (IELE) $[1^2]_{\ell^2/s^4}^{IELE}$ (T-R figure); such that available IELE cannot support the MWEP transformation in the $r < [2]_{\ell}$ region because the transformation in this region would require higher than the available IELE, $[2]_{\ell^3/s^2}/[r]_{\ell} > [1]_{\ell^2/s^2}^{IELE}$ (blue circle T-R figure, figure (b)). Hence, gravitational potentials have non-zero-singularities $[2]_{\ell}$;
- **Multiple pairs of gravitational potentials:** gravitational potentials comes in pairs: entangled and complementary, contractive and expansive, gravitational potentials pairs with complementary domain spatial unit (DSU): Newtonian gravity only describe the contractive macroscopic DcO-MWEP;
- **Faster than light:** High order gravities are faster than light at $[(32\pi)^{\#}c]_{m/s}$ with $\#$ denoting the E-domain order ([1].X.C.5); Newtonian gravity model posits that the speed of gravity is infinite, and the GR posits that gravity travels at the speed of light. (note that an astronomical gravity speed $[2(32\pi)^5c]_{m/s}$ has been observed*).

Section 4

Why GR is incomplete

Subatomic and astronomic relativistic adjustments partially address near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (NSTEE):

- *Monochromic* relativistic adjustments (B-R figure*¹) can address *some* EIDIP effects in the ruly region (T-R figure), but they **cannot** fully address the **direction and sign changing** of the NSTEEs and nondecaying EIDIP effects (e.g., $P_r^\infty \propto r^0$); such that GR and conventional models need **time dilation** and **form factors** to explain observed NSTEE induced phenomena, e.g., conventional [black hole models](#) need **form factors** to remove the singularity and to makes gravity *repulsive* at very small distances (M-R figure, [1].X.D.4);
- **Relativistic adjustments still need formfactors**; e.g., relativistic effects are found to decrease the **formfactor** for light nuclei but to increase the **formfactor** for heavy nuclei*²; ditto for classical electrodynamics: e.g., the neutron and proton charge distribution **formfactors** ([1].VIII.A-D);
- New dark matter map reveals the matter isn't as clumpy as expected – there are hints that it is smoother; which could imply that there's something wrong with Einstein's theory of relativity;
- The “new” **field theory***³ $A \approx -\alpha/r$, which **describes** the ruly long-range xE-domain EIDIP effects $P_E^\infty \propto 1/r$, can replace GR to describe the precession of Mercury and bending of light; which affirms that GR is only describe the ruly subset of the xE-domain EIDIP effects;
- High-order MWEF and EIDIP effects travel faster than light at $[(32\pi)^\# c]_{m/s}$ with # denoting the E-domain order ([1].X.C.5) (note that an astronomical gravity speed $[2(32\pi)^5 c]_{m/s}$ has been **observed**). In comparison, the GR posits that gravity travels at the speed of light.

Section 4

*¹ https://newt.phys.unsw.edu.au/einsteinlight/jw/module4_time_dilation.htm; *²:<https://arxiv.org/abs/0908.1535>; *³ <https://www.mae.ncsu.edu/eischen/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2020/12/PhysicsEssaysSilverbergEischen2020.pdf>

Why QM and SM are incomplete

Quantum mechanics and subatomic relativistic adjustments partially address subatomic near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (NSTEEs):

- The connections between the forces and phenomena induced by the strange “short-range turbulent and object-asymmetrical” and “long-range ruly and object-symmetrical” of the EIDIP effects are unknown to current physics and lead to disparate conventional physics models to describe them; ([1].X.C.2)
- *Monochromic* subatomic relativistic adjustments (T-R figure*¹) can address some EIDIP effects in the ruly region (T-R figure), but they **cannot** fully address the **direction and sign changing** of the NSTEEs and nondecaying EIDIP effects;
- **Relativistic adjustments still need formfactors**; e.g., relativistic effects are found to decrease the **formfactor** for light nuclei but to increase the **formfactor** for heavy nuclei*²; : e.g., the neutron charge distribution **formfactors** which are produced by the expulsive and attritive subatomic EIDIP effects (M-R figure) ([1].VIII.A-D);
- Even with subatomic relativistic adjustments, QM still can not fully explain the subatomic NSTEEs (B-R figure); e.g., QM still requires a hypothetical *expulsive* Yukawa gravitational potential with hypothetical negative mass to explain the expulsive nuclear foce;
- Ditto for classical electrodynamics; e.g., the virtual photon mass measurements actually measured the deviation between the defined Coulibiatic constant and the settle-to-constant (but not real constant) of long-range EIDIP effect coupling;
- That the anomalous Magnetic Moment (AMM) of the Muon discrepancy between the SM's prediction and measurements indicates new physics beyond the standard model; and the EIDIP framework can explain the Muon's AAM..

Section 4

*¹ https://newt.phys.unsw.edu.au/einsteinlight/jw/module4_time_dilation.htm; *² <https://arxiv.org/abs/0908.1535>; *³ <https://www.mae.ncsu.edu/eischen/wp-content/uploads/sites/17/2020/12/PhysicsEssaysSilverbergEischen2020.pdf>

Criteria and obstacles in evaluating scientific claims

There is a significant amount of human interpretation in the sciences; these are criteria to judge the merit and meaning of a scientific claim:

- **Where did the data come from?** The 10+ EEPTs are based on publicly available and well received data sets and papers;
- **How was the data collected and handled?** Those publicly available data sets and papers meet the accepted publication standard;
- **How exceptional/irrefutable is the data?** publicly available and well received data sets and papers;
- **Are the results statistically significant?** 7+ Sigma.
- How significant is the significance? Statistically “proof” that EIDIP does exist;
- **Were the results confirmed by an independent experiment?** The objectivity of MATLAB simulations are inarguable; those 10+ EEPTs can be verified with publicly available data.

There Obstacles in accepting new scientific discoveries: e.g.,

- **Incommensurability:** New discovery may require to used new terminology that hinders the understanding and acceptancy of the new theories, especially those as disruptive ones; e.g., the EIDIP framework employs new terms or short-hands (e.g., MWEF, EIDIP, NSTEE, E-domain) that are not in the conventional models but necessary to efficiently explain the framework;
- **Human factor:** The “utilities” aspect of new discoveries may hinder the *personal* utilities aspect of scientists; e.g., a string theorist’s prodigious reputation will be affected because that, to unify gravity and other fundamental interactions does not require esoteric abstract math and the unintuitive 11 dimensions (it only require simple calculus math per EIDIP framework); i.e., because the unorthodox and disruptive nature of the EIDIP framework, accepting it will shaken physicists out of their comfort zones;
- **“If the new framework can solve this problem, then I will take it serious”:** the nascent two-body EIDIP framework is **yet** to explain a long list of physical few-body interaction phenomena and mysteries.

Discussion and FAQ

Why grand unified theory is so allusive

Gravity and other forces have parent-to-child relationship such that the peer-to-peer GUT approaches based on incomplete conventional models would be fruitless:

- The main reason why the GUT is elusive is because of the wrong assumption that gravity and other fundamental forces has a peer-to-peer relationship compares to their actual parent-child relationship;
- Both the QM, Newtonian gravity, and GR partially describe the observed EIDIP effects, i.e., they are incomplete models, such that those GUT based on which would contain artifacts, e.g., 11 dimensions and relativistic time dilation and direction ([1].X.D.17); such that these attempts would be fruitless;
- The EIDIP framework includes a quantitative simple calculus EIDIP equation ([1].equ.19) and a qualitative EIDIP framework ([1].II. IV, IX) accompany with 10+ computational (MATLAB, [2]) phenomenological test cases against real-world measurements ([1].V-VIII) that “prove” the unification of forces with 7+ sigma statistical significance level (updated from [1].X.B);
- The derivation of the EIDIP ([1].equ.19) and the 10+ EEPTs have revealed that gravity and other fundamental forces have a **parent-child** relationship in contrast to the **peer-to-peer** (all merged at high energy) relationship assumption of conventional unify models; i.e., **gravity is the only fundamental force**.

Section 5

QM uncertainty principle and EIDIP framework

Deterministic EIDIP framework does not conflict with uncertainty principle and observer effect.

- QM uncertainty principle reflects the turbulent NSTEEs; EM models describe the long-range ruly EIDIP (T-R figure);
- Although based on deterministic EIDIP effects equations, the EIDIP framework does not violate the quantum uncertainty principle because the MWEP underlying the EIDIP possesses the particle-wave **duality** (E-fermion $r < [2]_{\ell}$ and E-boson $r > [2]_{\ell}$, B-R figure), and the uncertainty principle is inherent in the properties of all wave-like systems*. Furthermore, a physical measurement always takes part in certain E-domains that come with the energy resolution and DSU limit;
- The EIDIP framework supports the physical observer effect that observing a phenomenon changes the phenomenon necessarily; this is because, in addition to the angular-EIDIP axis-asymmetric nudging (AEAAN) effects and OSPD-misalignment oscillations, the short-range NSTEE effects between the target and test particles' close encounters will change the target's position and momentum and induce uncertainties in measurements.

Interdomain MWEPs' jump-singularity

The magnitude-discontinuity at singularity (jump-singularity) is a good approximation:

- Although a MWEP does not have a discontinuity singularity (red curve, T-R figure), a MWEP measured from different E-domains can have jump-singularity (blue curve, T-R figure) because the interdomain coupling T_c affects the interdomain energy measurements. However, because that there is NO infinite energy existing in nature, jump-singularity does not exist in nature;
- The EPNCR-EEPT has revealed that the nucleons within matters tend to have shell structures, i.e., they clamp together at the E-fermion radius $[2]_\ell$ (green box, T-R figure), such that they have little effects on the jumping-slope (blue dashed-arrow);
- For the xE-domain MWEPs, astronomical objects' radii (light blue box near origin) are relatively way smaller than the xE-domain DSU; such that their radii have little effects on the jumping-slope (blue dashed-arrow, T-R figure); e.g., in the PSAA-EEPT, Sun's radius $[6.96342e8]_m = [4.5966e-4]_{Dx2}$, which is 2175.5 times smaller than the Dx2-DSU, that the normalized angular-EIDIP effect, which is produced with the MWEP with jump-singularity (blue curve, T-R figure), can still trace the "anomalous" Pioneer spacecrafts 10/11 sunward accelerations (M-R figure);
- For those system with distributed mass spread over multiple xE-DSU (e.g., Milky Way mass distribution, $[1]_{kpc} \approx [20]_{Dx5}$), they can smear the EIDIP effect (e.g., the width of MWRC peak is wider than the normalize P_r peak, B-R figure), but the underlying EIDIP effects are still visible (green curve).

Why gravity is much weaker than other forces

In short, gravity is an at-point (local) gradient induced forces; whereas the force induced by the EIDIP effects are regional interaction energy potential, EIDIP, induced forces:

- The **regional** interaction energy differential produced EIDIP (T-R figure) induced force (e.g., angular-EIDIP induced strong force, M-R figure) would be naturally greater than the **at-point** local MWEP gradient induced gravity (B-R figure).

Discussion and FAQ

Can EIDIP framework explain QM, GR, etc.?

The QM and GR partially describe the observed subatomic NSTEES and astronomic EIDIP effects respectively.

- Because that the EIDIP framework has 7+ Sigma significance level and can unify all fundamental forces including the strong force (L1 figure) and residual strong force (L2 figure), the EIDIP effects does exist (and detectable) in subatomic level such that the EIDIP effects must be related to the observed QM phenomena;
- The near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (**NSTEE**) (L3 figure) are the building blocks underly the observed phenomena that implicated those 100+ particles. I.e., Analog to a restaurant menu, the EIDIP effects are the *integrants*; whereas the composite EIDIP effects produced the observed behaviors of 100+ particles are the *menu items*;

- The neutron and proton charge distribution (NCD and PCD) EEPs have revealed that the observed expulsive and attractive behaviors in those particle “charges” measurements are actually produced by the expulsive and attractive EIDIP effects (L4 figure) ([1].VIII.A-D);
- The expulsive EIDIP effects in the NSTEE region can explain the hadron and astrophysical jets (L5 figure);
- The short-range near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (NSTEE) are object-asymmetrical such that they induced the observed charge parity (CP) violation ([1].III.A.1).

Section 5

Do photons have mass

Photons, like other matter and energy entities, possess MWEPs of which the particle-like E-fermion core and the wave-like E-boson field; i.e., they have (interaction) mass.

- The NCD (T-R figure) and PCD EEPTs have revealed that Coulomb's Law is not accurate in subatomic range; the observed “charge” behaviors are produced by the EIDIP effects couplings;
- The EEC-EEPT revealed that Coulombic coupling constant describes the long-range settle-to-constant EIDIP effect coupling $r^2 P_d^\infty \propto r^0$ that is not a real constant (green line, M-R figure). In that sense, the Coulomb's coupling constant is not accurate in subatomic or even in meter range; furthermore, EIDIP effects permeate (subatomic to astronomical) space of which the coupling further muddles the virtual photon mass measurements;
- Those virtual photon mass measurements based on Coulombic constant would contain OEIAs; For those photon's “rest-mass” measurements based on the Coulomb's Law, the measured photon rest-mass” limits are the unavoidable meter-range distance-variant EIDIP coupling deviation from the ‘constant” and environmental EIDIP effects;
- The astronomical radio emissions' frequency-dependent time delays can be influenced by the “the electron column density” along the path AND the permeating astronomical EIDIP effects; For those photon rest-mass measurements based on which, their photon “rest-mass” limit measurements include the unavoidable astronomical expansive distance-variant EIDIP effects of astronomical bodies along the path.

Discussion and FAQ

xE-EIDIP effects underlying Cosmic large structures

Alternative gravity theories for dark matter must fit our cosmological observations; e.g., cosmic large structures.

- Some xE-EIDIP effects, although energy-leaky (i.e., will consume energy), have settled to constant behaviors that they travel faster than light speed $[(32\pi)^{\#}c]_{m/s}$ and can reach “unlimited” range as long as there is enough energy between these interacting galaxies (e.g., angular momentum); e.g., the angular-EIDIP effect underlying the Pioneer spacecrafts anomalies (B-R figure) where the required energy is provided by the on-board energy source (to keep the rotating antenna always pointing to Sun). Such that xE-domain angular-EIDIP effects induced attractive force would travel faster than light, be able to reach intergalactic range, and support the observed cosmic large structure formations.

The xE-EIDIP effects underlying the MWRC anomalies can explain the lower end of cosmic void.

- If we put two MW side-by-side and touch at the 10% gravity distance $[1343]_{kpc}$ (green vertical dashed line, figure below), the cosmic void between the observable MW is about $[2.686]_{Mpc}$ which compares with the lower range cosmic void of $[10]_{Mpc}$.

Section 5

Object-asymmetrical NSTEE and CP violation

Short-range near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (NSTEE) are object-asymmetrical (target-centric, T-R figure, reference-centric, B-R figure).

- The observed CP symmetry violation is a signature of the electroweak interaction;
- The 10+ EEPTs have revealed that EIDIP effects underly the EM and weak interaction; hence, the object-asymmetrical NSTEEs could also underly the CP symmetry violation.

Tidal forces are EIDIP effect induced force

Tidal forces are EIDIP effect induced force.

- The gravity varies inversely as the square of the distance;
- The tidal force, a force that stretches a body towards and away from the center of mass of another body, is explained conventionally due to a *gradient* in the gravitational field of the other body; The tidal forces is modeled as a force vary inversely as the cube of the distance;
- As in the near earth fly by anomalies are likely produced by the moon-centric EIDIP effects (T-R figure, slide #), the tidal force are also produced by other-body centric EIDIP effects.

Anti-gravity Effect Measured In Lab?

Scientists funded by the European Space Agency have measured the gravitational equivalent of a magnetic field for the first time in a laboratory (2006).*

- In the EIDIP framework, EIDIP effects have symmetrical behaviors in cE- and xE-domains; e.g., both the astrophysical jets of black holes and the subatomic hadron jets are produced by the symmetrical xE- and cE-domain turbulent and sign changing EIDIP effects in the NSTEE region (T-R figure);
- The measured anti-gravity effects from gravitational equivalent of a magnetic field, are produced by cE-domain expulsive EIDIP effects (B-R figure);
- They also found that, under certain special conditions, the effect is much larger than expected from general relativity; this is because GR is an incomplete theory such that its monochromatic relativistic adjustments cannot cover the turbulent and sign-changing of EIDIP effects in the NSTEEs region (slide #); hence, the GR's prediction would contain OEIAs such that its predictions would NOT match the the measurements.

EIDIP framework papers links

- Zenodo.org EIDIP community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eidip/>
 - [1] : <https://zenodo.org/record/3471904> A gravitational interaction potential unifies gravity with other forces: The cornerstone of Theory of Everything
 - [2] : <https://zenodo.org/record/3471963#.YGy6jj9ICUn> A gravitational interaction potential unifies gravity with other forces--MATLAB program and figures
- ResearchGate personal website: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Michael-Hwang-5>
- ResearchGate EIDIP project: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/E-space-Inter-Domain-Interaction-potential-the-connector-among-gravity-other-forces-and-non-classical-physical-phenomenas>
- Academia personal website: <https://independent.academia.edu/MichaelYTHwang>

Phenomenological test cases abbreviation table

EEPT	Remark
EEC	Effective electrostatic coupling, GEC: gravitoelectric coupling;
EMC	Effective magnetic coupling, GMC: gravitomagnetic coupling;
ERC	Effective residual-strong coupling, GMC: gravitoresidualstrong coupling;
ESC	Effective strong coupling, GMC: gravitostrong coupling;
IACF	Interatomic covalent force;
MWRC	Milky Way rotation curve; RC: rotation curve;
EEC	Effective electrostatic coupling, GEC: gravitoelectric coupling;
EMC	Effective magnetic coupling, GMC: gravitomagnetic coupling;
ERC	Effective residual-strong coupling, GRC: gravitoresidualstrong coupling;
ESC	Effective strong coupling, GSC: gravitostrong coupling;
GW	Gravity wave
IACF	Interatomic covalent force;
NBE	Nuclear binding energy;
NCD	Neutron charge distribution;
NCR	Nuclear charge radii;
NEFA	Near-Earth flybys' speed anomalies, NEAR: a case of near-Earth flybys;
NGCD	Newtonian gravitational constant deviation, aka GCCD: gravitational coupling constant deviation;

EEPT	Remark
NNP	Neutron-neutron Potential, aka RSF: residual-strong force or nuclear force;
PCD	Proton charge distribution;
PSAA	Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomaly, aka SWAA: sunward acceleration anomaly
SF	Strong force;

Abbreviation table

Abbrev.	Remark
ADND13	The 2013 Atomic Data and Nuclear Data;
AEAAN	Angular EIDIP axis-asymmetric nudging (effect);
AEG	Angular EIDIP-gradient (effect);
AIRT	Angular isotropic residual tension;
AMDC	The Atomic Mass Data Center;
AME2012	The 2012 Atomic Mass Evaluation table, AME2012e: AME2012 with experimental values;
APA	Angular EIDIP induced acceleration, APC: APA coupling;
BFA	Beat frequency amplitude (of gravity waves);
E-domain	Energy domain
E-space	Energy space
CM	Effective central mass (galactic disk mass model);
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Council for Science;
DSU	E-domain spatial unit;
EEPT	EIDIP effects phenomenological test
EIDIP	E-space Inter-Domain Interaction Potential,
EM	Electromagnetic;
GFR	Gravitational force ripple;
GR	General relativity;
IDTC	Inter-domain transfer coupling, aka T_c ;
IELT	Isotropic E-space linear tension, IELTS: IELT tensile stress, IELE: Isotropic E-space linear energy;
IMOI	Interaction moments of inertia (MOI);
LBID	Lower bound inter-elementary-particle distance $R_u = 1/c^2$

Abbrev.	Remark
LCEN	Long-range composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing
MW	Milky Way
MWEP	Matter Warped E-space potential,
NLU	Natural length unit, aka DSU;
NSTEE	Near-singularity turbulent EIDIP effects;
OCF	Origin centripetal force, e.g., gravity-OCF;
OEIA	Omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts;
PGA	EIDIP-gradient effect induced acceleration, PGC: PGA coupling;
QCD	Quantum chromodynamics;
QFT	Quantum field theory;
RAVE-DR2	CDS J/A+A/511/A90 RAVE DR2 distance catalogue
RBAA	Radial bin-averaged absolute (MW stars' RC)
RQ	Radial-quadratic (galactic disk mass model);
RL	Radial-linear (galactic disk mass model);
RC	Rotation curve;
RV	Rotational velocity;
SEF	Semi-empirical formula, EPNBE-SEF: EIDIP based NBE-SEF, EPNCR-SEF: EEPT-parameters based NCR-SEF, SWNCR-SEF: Weizsacker-Skyrme mass model produced NCR-SEF of [11];
SM	Standard model;
SR	Special relativity